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Deep decarbonisation of regional energy systems: a novel modelling approach and its application to the Italian energy transition

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Abstract

Deep decarbonisation – i.e. the transition towards net-zero emissions energy systems – will be enabled by a high penetration of intermittent renewables, storage and sector-coupling technologies. In this paper, we present a novel modelling approach to capture the increasing complexity of such future energy systems and help policy makers choose among the different possible transition scenarios. Salient features of our model, consisting of an extended and regionalised version of EnergyScope [1], are a low computational time and a concise formulation which make it suitable for uncertainty and *what-if* analyses. As a case study, the model is applied to devise scenarios for the Italian energy transition. Specifically, we develop the first open-source whole-energy system model of Italy and assess the feasibility of its decarbonisation strategy with respect to uncertainties in the deployment of carbon capture and storage (CCS) and renewable technologies. Results show that emissions can be cut by 79-97% vs. 1990 levels thanks to a radical electrification of the energy system coupled to a wide deployment of renewables and efficient energy conversion technologies. Finally, we discuss the synergies, advantages and disadvantages of our proposed approach with respect to alternative modelling approaches used across 88 recent deep decarbonisation studies. The analysis suggests that our model, thanks to its computational efficiency and a *snapshot* approach (i.e., modelling a target-year in the future), can complement more detailed

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and established energy models optimising the energy transition *pathway* (i.e., modelling the pathway from today to the target year).

Highlights

- Novel open-source whole-energy system model for deep decarbonisation studies
- Key features: hourly resolution, target-year optimisation, computational efficiency
- Case study: deep decarbonisation of Italy in 2050 under uncertainty
- Results: 79-97% CO₂ emission reduction is feasible and cost-effective
- Comparison with other models used in 88 recent deep decarbonisation studies

Keywords: Energy planning, Energy transition, Decarbonization, Energy systems, Energy modeling, Italy, Uncertainty

Word Count: 7529

List of acronyms and abbreviations

CCGT	Combined cycle gas turbine
CCS	Carbon capture and storage
CHP	Cogeneration of heat and power
DHN	District heating network
EU	European Union
EUD	End-use demand
EV	Electric vehicle
GHG	Greenhouse gas
HP	Heat pump
LP	Linear programming
NG	Natural gas
PV	Photovoltaic

RE	Renewable energy
RES	Renewable energy source
TD	Typical day
TES	Thermal energy storage
TPES	Total primary energy supply
TS	Time slices

1. Introduction

The impact of human activities on our planet has become more and more observable, causing dramatic and rapid changes to the climate as well as bringing serious hazards for human health [2, 3]. This implies that drastically reducing the levels of heat-trapping gasses in the atmosphere (*mitigation*) and coping with the already present consequences of climate change (*adaptation*) are fundamental drivers that will characterise international policies in the next few decades. The 2015 Paris Agreement on Climate Change calls for a sharp reduction in global fossil CO₂ emissions to keep the global average temperature rise in this century below 2°C compared to pre-industrial levels; for developed countries, this translates to a 70-95% emission cut with respect to 1990 [4]. In this context, the European Union (EU) has taken on a global leadership role and is now committed to an 80-95% reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 2050 [5, 6].

Reaching such ambitious decarbonisation targets, which we refer to as *deep decarbonisation*, will require profound structural changes for regional and national energy systems. In fact, this “*pathway toward the transformation of the global energy sector from fossil-based to zero-carbon*” [7] aims at eventually reducing the levels of anthropogenic GHG emissions to zero thanks to energy efficiency measures, a better management of energy demand and an increased penetration of renewable energy sources (RESs). As a result, this *energy transition* implies a rising complexity along both the technical and the socio-economic dimensions due to the increasing cross-sectoral interactions and the penetration of new technologies in the market. In this context, national decarbonisation strategies and policies can be more robust

if based on the analysis of possible future scenarios developed with the support of mathematical energy models [8, 9], which can help understand these climate-energy dynamics and plan future energy systems.

With the present paper, we contribute to this deep decarbonisation effort in two ways: first, we present an extended (*i.e.*, including more technologies and demand types) and regionalised version of the multi-sector multi-vector EnergyScope model [10, 1], an open-source linear programming (LP) modelling framework for the strategic planning of national energy systems. Thanks to a low computational time and a *snapshot* approach (*i.e.*, modelling a target-year in the future), the proposed model is particularly suitable for uncertainty and *what-if* analyses in the context of deep decarbonisation studies. Second, we apply this model to develop the first open-source whole-energy system model of Italy and devise deep decarbonisation scenarios under uncertainty for the Italian energy system.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. In Section 2 we review a large number of recent deep decarbonisation studies focusing on the adopted modelling approaches (*e.g.*, which model is used, key modelling choices, etc.), which allows us to identify the main challenges in this field; in this context, we analyse in further depth models and studies targeting the Italian energy system. In Section 3 we introduce our novel modelling approach. In Section 4, we apply our model to Italy and discuss deep decarbonisation scenarios for the Italian energy system; model and data are made available open-source [11] and are documented in the Supplementary Material. In Section 5 we critically discuss advantages and limitations of the proposed modelling approach in comparison to other existing and established energy models.

2. Literature review

2.1. Review of energy models used for deep decarbonisation studies

In this section, a large set of deep decarbonisation studies – *i.e.* studies *defining pathways to deeply reduce GHG emissions and highly increase RES penetration on a regional and national scale* – is reviewed. The systematic selection of studies to be reviewed was

conducted by searching the Web of Science (WoS) and Google Scholar databases by combining the following keywords: “100% renewable”, “energy”, “scenarios”, “energy system(s)”, “modelling”, “long-term”, “planning”, “decarbonisation”, “2050”. These search terms were chosen based on our previous experience with the scientific literature in the field of energy modelling and energy transition studies.

In order to include only the most recent deep decarbonisation studies, developed with currently available and actively used energy models, four screening criteria were additionally set: (i) we limited the review to studies published in the last ten years (after 2009), in order to consider only the most recent literature that is representative of the current state-of-the-art in terms of technologies, climate-energy directives, costs and emission reduction targets; (ii) scenarios must have been developed adopting a well-referenced energy system model, describing the adopted methodology in terms of spatial and temporal resolution, decarbonisation and/or renewable penetration targets, sectors covered, and main assumptions; (iii) for the spatial scale, scenarios must consider large-scale demand areas such as whole nations, or covering extended regions within large nations (i.e. excluding scenarios for individual cities, small islands, etc.) of the European continent; (iv) scenarios were required to target the year 2050 or earlier in order to evaluate short-to-medium term strategies and pathways of decarbonisation according to European directives.

Table 2 lists and classifies the 88 studies which were selected based on the aforementioned screening criteria. The classification criteria are merged from different sources [12, 13, 14], with the aim of providing a broad set of indicators to characterise the main features of the different energy models as well as the key modelling choices. The classification criteria are: (i) year of publication; (ii) energy model used; (iii) studied energy system and time horizon; (iv) temporal resolution; (v) spatial resolution; (vi) main objective in terms of emissions reduction or RES penetration; (vii) considered energy sectors.

According to these classification criteria, the 88 reviewed studies make use of 28 different energy system models (not counting the EnergyScope model, which we present in the next Section); note that, if more than one model is used in a given study, only the core model is ac-

Table 2: Review of national/regional deep decarbonisation studies. Abbreviations: publication (Pub.), resolution (Res.), hours (h), days (d), years (y), typical days (TDs), time slices (TS). “-” indicates that information was not found.

Study	Year of Pub.	Model	Target		Time Res.	Regionalised?	Objective ^a	Sectors		
			Spatial	Temporal				Power	Heat	Mobility
Connolly et al. [15]	2011	EnergyPLAN	Ireland	2030	h	✗	100% RE	✓	✓	✓
Child and Breyer [16]	2016	EnergyPLAN	Finland	2050	h	✗	100% RE	✓	✓	✓
Lund and Mathiesen [17]	2009	EnergyPLAN	Denmark	2050	h	✗	100% RE	✓	✓	✓
Čosić et al. [18]	2012	EnergyPLAN	Macedonia	2050	h	✗	100% RE	✓	✓	✓
Fernandes and Ferreira [19]	2014	EnergyPLAN	Portugal	2022	h	✗	100% RE	✓		
Calise et al. [20]	2017	EnergyPLAN & TRNSYS	Italy	2050	h	✗	80% GHG reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Krajačić et al. [21]	2011	EnergyPLAN	Croatia	2020	h	✗	100% RE	✓	✓	✓
Gota et al. [22]	2011	EnergyPLAN	Romania	2020	h	✗	Increasing RE	✓	✓	✓
Kwon and Østergaard [23]	2012	EnergyPLAN	Denmark	2050	h	✗	100% RE	✓	✓	✓
Connolly et al. [24]	2016	EnergyPLAN	EU-28	2050	h	✗	100% RE	✓	✓	✓
Hansen et al. [25]	2019	EnergyPLAN	Germany	2050	h	✗	100% RE	✓	✓	✓
Prina et al. [26]	2019	EnergyPLAN (EPLANopt)	Italy	2050	h	✗	40% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Anjo et al. [27]	2018	OSeMOSYS	Portugal	2050	96 TS	✗	Carbon Free	✓		
Welsch et al. [28]	2014	OSeMOSYS	Ireland	2050	12 TS	✗	80% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓		
Gardumi et al. [29]	2019	OSeMOSYS	Italy	2040	16 TS	✗	High RE	✓		
Navas-Anguita et al. [30]	2018	LEAP-OSeMOSYS	Spain	2050	-	✗	Low-carbon mobility	✓		✓
García-Gusano et al. [31]	2016	LEAP-OSeMOSYS	Spain	2030	-	✗	40% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓		
García-Gusano and Iribarren [32]	2018	LEAP-OSeMOSYS	Spain	2030	-	✗	90% REST ^c	✓		
Kumar and Madlener [33]	2018	LEAP-OSeMOSYS	Germany	2050	16 TS	✗	80-95% GHG reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Bartholdsen et al. [34]	2019	GENeSYS-MOD	Germany	2050	16 TS	✓	80-95% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Hainsch et al. [35]	2018	GENeSYS-MOD	EU-28	2050	16 TS	✓	80 CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Colbertaldo et al. [36]	2018	Developed by the authors	Italy	2050	h	✓	80% GHG reduction ^b	✓		✓
Colbertaldo et al. [37]	2020	Developed by the authors	Italy	2050	h	✓	50% low-C mobility	✓		✓
Teske et al. [38]	2020	[R]E 24/7	Italy	2050	h	✓	100% RE	✓	✓	✓
Vellini et al. [39]	2020	Developed by the authors	Italy	2030	y	✗	47% GHG reduction ^b	✓		
Spiecker and Weber [40]	2014	E2M2s	EU ^d	2050	h (TDs)	✓	80-95% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓	✓	
Pfenninger and Keirstead [41]	2015	Calliope	UK	2050	h ^e	✓	Maximise RE	✓		
Lombardi et al. [42]	2020	Calliope	Italy	2050	h	✓	100% RE	✓		
Bramstoft and Skytte [43]	2017	STREAM	Sweden	2050	h	✗	Low-carbon mobility			✓
Pedersen and Skytte [44]	2016	STREAM	Sweden	2050	h	✗	Low-carbon mobility			✓
Poncelet et al. [45]	2016	TIMES	Belgium	2055	12 TS	✗	50% RE	✓		
Devogelaer [46]	2012	TIMES	Belgium	2050	78 TS	✗	100% RE	✓	✓	✓
Rečka and Štasný [47]	2016	TIMES	Czech Republic	2050	36 TS	✗ ^f	80% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓	✓	
Seljom and Rosenberg [48]	2018	TIMES	Scandinavia ^g	2050	48 TS	✓	100% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Chiodi et al. [49]	2013	Irish-TIMES	Ireland	2050	12 TS	✗	80-95% CO ₂ reduction	✓	✓	✓
Pursiheimo et al. [50]	2017	TIMES-VTT	Nordic Countries ^h	2050	10 TS	✓	100% RE	✓	✓	✓
Petrović and Karlsson [51]	2016	TIMES-DK	Denmark	2050	32 TS	✓	100% RE	✓	✓	✓
Labriet et al. [52]	2010	TIMES-SP	Spain	2020	12 TS	✗	20% RE	✓	✓	✓
Amorim et al. [53]	2014	TIMES-PT/SP	Portugal & Spain	2050	288 TS	✗	Carbon Free	✓		
Fortes et al. [54]	2019	TIMES-PT	Portugal	2050	12 TS	✗	80% GHG reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Fortes et al. [55]	2013	TIMES-PT & GEM-E3	Portugal	2050	12 TS & y	✗	60% GHG reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Krook Riekkola et al. [56]	2011	TIMES-Sweden	Sweden	2020	12 TS	✗	40% GHG reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Krakowski et al. [57]	2016	TIMES-FR	France	2050	84 TS	✗	100% RE	✓		
Assoumou and Maizi [58]	2011	TIMES-FR	France	2050	-	✗	60% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Virdis [59]	2015	TIMES & GDyn-E/ICES	Italy	2050	12 TS	✗	80% GHG reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Pina et al. [60]	2013	TIMES & EnergyPLAN	Portugal	2050	288 TS	✗	30% CO ₂ reduction ⁱ	✓		

^aFor GHG reduction, only the most ambitious target scenario is considered.

^bWith respect to 1990 emissions level.

^cRenewable Energy Security Index.

^dSpecific focus on Germany.

^eResolution reduced from 8784 to 550 time steps. Only days of low wind availability at hourly resolution.

^fOnly heat demand and production are regionalised.

^gNorway, Denmark, Sweden.

^hNorway, Denmark, Sweden, Finland.

ⁱWith respect to 2005 emissions level.

Study	Year of Pub.	Model	Target		Time Res.	Regionalized?	Objective ^a	Sectors		
			Spatial	Temporal				Power	Heat	Mobility
Tigas et al. [61]	2015	TIMES & ProPSim	Greece	2050	y ^j	✓	RES Maximisation	✓	✓	✓
Simoes et al. [62]	2014	JRC-EU-TIMES	EU-28	2050	12 TS	✓	85% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓		
Moore et al. [63]	2018	UKTM ^c & highRES	UK	2050	16 TS ^j	✓	80% GHG reduction ^b	✓		
Zeyringer et al. [64]	2018	UKTM ^c & highRES	UK	2050	16 TS ^j	✓	50-80% RE	✓		
Pye [65]	2015	UKTM ^c	UK	2050	16 TS	✗	80% GHG reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Usher and Strachan [66]	2011	UKTM ^c	UK	2050	16 TS	✗	90-95% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Ekins et al. [67]	2011	UKTM ^c	UK	2050	16 TS	✗	90% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Ekins et al. [68]	2013	UKTM ^c	UK	2050	16 TS	✗	80-90% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Li and Trutnevyte [69]	2017	UKTM ^c & D-EXPANSE	UK	2050	16 TS	✗	80% GHG reduction ^b	✓		
Anable et al. [70]	2012	UKTCM ^d	UK	2050	16 TS	✗	80% GHG reduction ^b			✓
RSE [71]	2017	TIMES (Monet) & REMod	Italy	2050	12 TS	✗ ^e	80% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Lanati and Gaeta [72]	2020	TIMES & sMTSIM	Italy	2050	12 TS	✗	100% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Landis et al. [73]	2019	TIMES (STEM) ^f	Switzerland	2050	144 TS	✗	70-85% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Kannan and Turton [74]	2014	TIMES (STEM) ^f	Switzerland	2050	144 TS	✗	60% CO ₂ reduction ^g	✓	✓	✓
Rodriguez et al. [75]	2016	TIMES (ETM-UCL) ^h	UE-28	2050	6 TS	✓	80% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Weidmann [76]	2013	SMM ⁱ	Switzerland	2050	6 TS	✗	60% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Siskos et al. [77]	2018	PRIMES	EU-28 ^l	2050	y	✓	80% GHG reduction ^b			✓
Capros et al. [78]	2012	PRIMES	EU-28 ^l	2050	y	✓	80% GHG reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Romeo et al. [79]	2009	PRIMES	Spain	2050	y	✗	90% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓		
Capros et al. [80]	2014	PRIMES & TIMES-PanEU	EU-28 ^l	2050	y & 12 TS	✓/✓	80% GHG reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Spataru et al. [81]	2015	DECC 2050 Calculator	UK	2050	y	✗	80% GHG reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Barton et al. [82]	2018	DECC 2050 Calculator & UKTM ^c	UK	2050	y & 16 TS	✗	80% GHG reduction ^b	✓		
Criqui [83]	2015	Imaclim-R-France	France	2050	y ^j	✗	80% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Child et al. [84]	2017	LUT	Ukraine	2050	h	✗	100% RE	✓		
Pye et al. [85]	2015	ESME	UK	2050	10 TS	✓	80% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓
Palzer and Henning [86]	2014	REMod-D	Germany	2050	h	-	100% RE	✓	✓	
Quiggin and Buswell [87]	2016	SHED	UK	2050	h	✗ ^k	80% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓	✓	
Sithole et al. [88]	2016	Energy Optimisation Calculator	UK	2050	y	✗	80% GHG reduction ^b	✓		
Pfluger et al. [89]	2011	PowerACE-Europe	EU-27 ^l	2050	h	✓	95% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓		
Zappa et al. [90]	2019	PLEXOS	EU-28 ^l	2050	h	✓	100% RE	✓		
Louis et al. [91]	2020	POLES & EUTGRID	UE-24	2050	h (12 TDs)	✓	80% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓		
Dagoumas and Barker [92]	2010	E3MG	UK	2050	y	✗	CO ₂ GHG reduction ^b	✓		✓
Tatarewicz et al. [93]	2019	MEESA ^m & d-PLACE	EU-28 ^{ln}	2050	9 TS	✓	80-95% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓	✓	
Haller et al. [94]	2012	LIMES-EU	EU-27 ^l & MENA ^o	2050	49 TS	✓	80% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓		
Jägemann et al. [95]	2013	DIMENSION	UE-27 ^l	2050	h (4 TDs)	✓	90% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓		
Pleßmann and Blechinger [96]	2017	elesplan-m	South-East-Europe	2050	h	✓	nearly-zero GHG reduction ^b	✓		
Krajačić et al. [97]	2011	H ₂ RES	Portugal	2020	h	✗	100% RE	✓		
Antosiewicz et al. [98]	2019	MEMO & MOEM	Poland	2050	y	✗	-	✓		
Jafari et al. [99]	2019	GenX	Italy	2050	h	✗	100% RE	✓		
Bompard et al. [100]	2020	GenX	Italy	2050	h	✗	68% CO ₂ reduction ^p	✓	✓	✓
Limpens et al. [1]	2019	EnergyScope	Switzerland	2035	h (TDs)	✗	50% RE	✓	✓	✓
Limpens et al. [13]	2020	EnergyScope	Belgium	2035	h (TDs)	✗	90% CO ₂ reduction ^b	✓	✓	✓

^aFor GHG reduction, only the most ambitious target scenario is considered.

^bWith respect to 1990 emissions level.

^cUK TIMES model.

^dUK transport carbon model.

^eOnly electricity demand and production are regionalized.

^fSwiss TIMES energy system model.

^gWith respect to 2010 emissions level.

^hEuropean TIMES model.

ⁱSwiss MARKAL Model.

^jOnly the electricity sector has an hourly load profile.

^kOnly renewable generation technologies are regionalised.

^lPlus Norway and Switzerland.

^mModel for European Energy System Analysis.

ⁿSpecific focus on Poland.

^oMiddle East/North Africa.

^pWith respect to 2015 emissions level

counted for. However, 19 of these models either use a top-down macro-econometric approach (e.g. E3MG [101]), or focus only – or mainly – on the power sector (e.g. PLEXOS [102], DIMENSION [103], Calliope [104], LUT [105], H2RES [106], GenX[107], [R]E 24/7, among others). For example, Calliope is a mature modelling framework mainly developed for – and mainly applied to – the power sector (however, the framework allows considering also other sectors). As such, these models are either not sufficiently rich in the way they characterise technologies, or do not fully account for cross-sectoral interactions, which limits their suitability for the development of low-carbon pathways at a whole-energy system scale; as a consequence, these models are not further investigated.

We thus restrict our analysis to the modelling frameworks and studies fully considering sector-coupling (i.e. accounting for power, heat and mobility sectors as well as their interaction), which is an important feature for the development of whole-energy national/regional deep decarbonisation pathways. These 9 remaining models are: EnergyPLAN, GENeSYS-MOD, OSeMOSYS, MARKAL/TIMES, PRIMES, DECC 2050 Calculator, Imaclim-R, ESME and STREAM. In the following, we briefly introduce and compare these 9 models in order to identify their main features and limitations.

According to our review, the MARKAL/TIMES [108] energy models family is the most widely used in the context of decarbonisation studies at a national/regional scale. MARKAL (acronym for MARKET ALlocation) [109] is a bottom-up model representing both the energy supply and demand sides of the energy system. The TIMES (The Integrated MARKAL-EFOM System) model [110, 111] is an evolution of MARKAL. It is a linear programming (LP) economic model generator that can be adapted to different energy systems at a national and regional level over a long, multi-period time horizon (usually 20–50 or 100 years); the model is mostly suitable for optimising investment decisions [112], while operation is represented in a coarser way using time slices (TS) [113]. MARKAL/TIMES is currently used by more than 70 countries [111], which often develop customised versions of the modelling framework in order to obtain a more detailed national characterisation.

A similar approach and structure is used at an European scale with the European TIMES

model – ETM-UCL [114, 115] – which represents the energy systems of 11 European regions covering the EU-28 member states plus Norway, Iceland and Switzerland. Each region in ETM-UCL has its own energy system and is able to trade fossil fuels, biomass and electricity. Additionally, the European Commission has so far mainly used the PRIMES model [116, 117], to develop low-carbon projections at the European level until 2050 by five-year periods [112]. It is a partial equilibrium modelling framework that simulates energy consumption and the energy supply system in the EU and in each of its member States.

Another widely used modelling tool in the European context is EnergyPLAN [118, 119], which can assist in the design of energy systems with high RES penetration. EnergyPLAN optimises the hourly operation of regional and national energy systems – including heat and electricity supply as well as the transport and industrial sectors – given the investment strategy as an input. As such, the model can be used to analyse and compare different investment strategies.

Overall, the three aforementioned energy models (MARKAL/TIMES, PRIMES and EnergyPLAN) represent the main energy sectors with high level of detail; however, these models and the related deep decarbonisation studies present also some shortcomings. First, the computational time varies from seconds (in the case of EnergyPLAN) to several minutes/hours (in the case of MARKAL/TIMES). Thus, while EnergyPLAN is suitable for quick scenario assessments (given the investment strategy as an input), many existing versions of TIMES need several hours to run [120], which limits the possibility of carrying out “what-if” or uncertainty analyses.

Second, in terms of time resolution, all the pathways devised using EnergyPLAN have an hourly resolution, which is suitable for evaluating both the integration of intermittent renewables (including heat and electricity storage) and the variability of demand. On the contrary, PRIMES simulates whole-year time periods (only the power and steam submodels can accommodate higher granularity [121]), while MARKAL and TIMES represent daily and seasonal variations in a rather coarse way by using time-slices [113]; hence, they are not perfectly suitable to evaluate close-to-100% renewable energy (RE) systems.

Third, in terms of spatial resolution, PRIMES allows to model a regionalised energy system; this means that, especially for large scale energy systems, PRIMES allows to evaluate strongly regional-dependent parameters such as demand, availability of resources and capacity of RESs. EnergyPLAN allows to coarsely disaggregate a country into sub-regions [122]. Several studies based on the TIMES energy systems model family take into account regional features: on the one hand, multi-regional versions of TIMES (e.g. TIMES-VTT [50], TIMES-DK [51], TIMES-PanEU [62] and ETM-UCL [75]) have been developed; on the other hand, one-region TIMES models can be integrated with other modelling tools (e.g. highRES [123]) in order to take into account zonal features of the power system (e.g. costs, generation capacities and locations).

Finally, EnergyPLAN, PRIMES and MARKAL/TIMES are not completely freely available and/or open-source (e.g. TIMES is freely downloadable but its input tools such as VEDA [111] are not). As a consequence, the results shown in the reported studies are often very difficult to compare and reproduce, both in terms of modelling approach and input data documentation; in this context, making models available open-source is increasingly valued and demanded by the energy modelling community [124, 125].

This last limitation applies also to Imaclim-R and ESME. Imaclim-R [126, 127] is a dynamic computable general equilibrium (CGE) model belonging to the Imaclim family of models developed at CIRED, and used in Criqui [83] to model the French energy system (Imaclim-R-France). It is a hybrid model which represents simultaneous changes in technology systems and the economy at a national scale, year by year from 2004 to 2050. The model allows an hourly resolution for the power sector, which makes it suitable for the assessment of high RE scenarios; however, being hourly defined only for the power sector, the Imaclim framework is not fully suitable to model the variability of heating/cooling demand and the integration of daily and seasonal thermal storage. In its current version Imaclim-R incorporates 12 regions for its macroeconomic module [126].

The Energy System Modelling Environment (ESME, [128]) has been developed specifically for the UK energy system. ESME is a multi-regional (12 regions in the UK), long-term,

least-cost optimisation model covering the whole energy system with 10 TS for the temporal resolution [14]; the latter, as discussed later in this Section, limits the representation of daily to seasonal storage options and intermittent RESs.

Moving on to the open-source energy planning tools, OSeMOSYS [129, 130] is a bottom-up, least-cost energy system optimisation framework for long-run integrated assessment and energy planning from the scale of continents (e.g. South America, EU-28) down to the scale of countries and regions. According to Prina et al. [131], OSeMOSYS has a high sector-coupling representation and a low resolution in technology characterisation; according to Groissböck [132], it is one of the very few open-source models which are mature enough for serious use. The modelling framework has been further developed in order to obtain the GENeSYS-MOD model [133]. Both OSeMOSYS and GENeSYS-MOD are open-source and freely available to the scientific community. Looking at the temporal resolution, both models optimise the investment strategy over multiple years and, similarly to other modelling frameworks (e.g., MARKAL/TIMES and ESME), estimate the operation cost based on time slices (the model is given as input the annual energy demand and a matrix that distributes this total demand over time slices during each year). *Time slices (TS)* are a combination of a season (e.g. summer/winter), a day type (e.g. weekend/weekday) and a daily time bracket (e.g. day/night); hence, one time slice could be “summer weekend night”. While TS allow to estimate the operating costs of the system, they “do not constitute a sequential and chronological representation of a year” [128], which makes it difficult for such models to capture the dynamics associated with the integration of intermittent renewables as well as the behaviour of daily and seasonal storage technologies (Kotzur et al. [134] discuss the challenges linked to the modelling of seasonal storage with independent typical periods, while Welsch et al. [135], Niet [136] and Kuling and Niet [137] address the implementation of storage in OSeMOSYS). Finally, looking at spatial resolution, OSeMOSYS can be used with a country-level resolution; GENeSYS-MOD can be scaled from small-scale applications, e.g., a company, up to the global energy system.

Finally, the DECC 2050 Calculator [138] and STREAM [139] are fast and relatively

simplified Excel-based modelling tools. The DECC 2050 Calculator, developed specifically for the UK, is a user-friendly one-region energy calculator with a yearly temporal resolution, which lets people create their own emission reduction pathways and evaluate their impact using well-documented scientific data. The DECC 2050 Calculator is more of a tool for engaging the public in the choices surrounding the UK energy transition rather than a proper energy planning tool. STREAM, originally developed for the Danish energy system, combines a yearly static “Energy Flow” model with an hourly “Duration Curve” sub-model to simulate different scenarios for a given target year and provide quick insights to support energy strategy decisions.

Table 3 summarizes the features of the 9 reviewed modelling frameworks, according to the following criteria: (i) open-source availability; (ii) optimisation of both the investment and the operation strategy; (iii) time granularity to model the integration of intermittent RES as well as daily and seasonal storage; (iv) spatial granularity (*i.e.*, regionalisation); (v) pathway (P) vs. snapshot (S), *i.e.* if the pathway from today to the target year is modelled, or only one target-year; (vi) computational time, and hence suitability for uncertainty applications needed for the development of reliable low-carbon scenarios at a national/regional scale.

2.2. Analysis of models and studies for the Italian energy system

Out of the 88 studies classified in Table 2, 13 focus on the Italian energy system. The main modelling framework used in these studies is TIMES/MARKAL (adopted in [71, 59, 72]), followed by EnergyPlan (adopted in [20, 26]), GenX (in [99, 100]), Calliope (in [42]), OSeMOSYS (in [29]), [R]E 24/7 (in [38]), while the remaining 3 studies use custom modelling frameworks. Although with different focuses, all these studies find that the deep decarbonisation of the Italian energy system is feasible and emission targets as high as 80-100% GHG reductions compared to 1990 can be reached.

Looking at relevant aspects for deep decarbonisation studies, out of these 13 works, 4 use open-source modelling frameworks (however, only Gardumi et al. [29] and Lombardi et al. [42] publish the code and data for the developed case studies); 6 adopt a whole-energy system approach, while the others focus only (or mostly) on the electricity sector;

Table 3: Comparison summary of the investigated energy system models. Legend: ✓ criterion satisfied; ✓ criterion partially satisfied; ✗ criterion not satisfied. Abbreviations: Optimisation (Optimis.), Regionalisation (Regional.), Computational (Comp.).

Model/Tool	Open Source	Optimis. (Model type)	Regional.	RES integration	Pathway/ Snapshot	Comp. time ^a
MARKAL/TIMES	✓ ^b	Investment ^c (LP)	✓ ^d	✓ ^e	P	mins-hours
PRIMES	✗	Market equilibrium (-)	✓	✗	P	-
EnergyPLAN	✓ ^f	Operation (-)	✓ ^g	✓	S	seconds
Imaclim-R	✗	Market equilibrium (-)	✓	✓ ^h	P	-
OSeMOSYS	✓	✓ (LP/MILP)	✓ ⁱ	✓ ^e	P	mins
GENeSYS-MOD	✓	✓ (LP)	✓	✓ ^e	P	mins
DECC 2050 Calc.	✓	✗	✗	✗	P	seconds
ESME	✗	✓(LP)	✓	✓ ^e	P	mins
STREAM	✓	✗	✗	✓ ^j	S	seconds

^aReported times are indicative as, in most cases, they depend on the specific case studies/input data (e.g., simple versions of TIMES take few minutes to run, while many existing versions need several hours [120])

^bThe core code is available open-source but using the model requires commercial pre-processing tools

^cOperation represented in a coarser way [112]

^dSome versions of the modelling framework are regionalised

^eTemporal resolution uses time-slices, which makes it more difficult to capture the dynamics associated with the integration of intermittent renewables and storage technologies.

^fThe tool is free to download and use, but the code is not released open-source

^gCoarse disaggregation of a country into sub-regions [122]

^hHourly resolution only for the power sector, thus suitable to model only iRES integration for electricity production.

ⁱAllows country-level resolution

^jThe hourly operation of the system is simulated by the “Duration Curve” submodel

4 subdivide the energy system into subregions, while the remainder consider national level data. Uncertainty is only considered in two studies: Lombardi et al. [42] develop sensitivity scenarios with respect to uncertainties in cost, demand and weather, while Vellini et al. [39] propose a parametric analysis to model the variation of mitigation costs as a function of both cost parameters and electricity mix configurations.

Based on our review, no open-source whole-energy system modelling framework for Italy has been developed to date.

3. EnergyScope: a novel modelling approach

As illustrated in Section 2.1, a large set of models is available for the strategic planning of regional and national energy systems. Historically, the different strengths of these models have enabled their use for multiple applications; however, our review identified as well some shortcomings, which limit a wider use of such models in the energy planning practice. In this context, the EnergyScope model – a novel modelling approach recently presented by Limpens et al. [1] building on previous work by Moret and coauthors [140, 10] – was developed to overcome some of these limitations. In this work, we present a spatially characterised version of EnergyScope, and propose it to model national energy systems with a significant regional characterisation.

3.1. General description and features

EnergyScope is a bottom-up LP modelling framework for the long-term planning of large-scale energy systems. As reviewed in Table 2, it has already been used to devise energy transition scenarios for European energy systems. The multi-vector modelling framework, accounting for sector-coupling, has been specifically designed to assess deep decarbonisation scenarios with high penetration rates of new technologies – such as intermittent renewables and storage – expected to play a central role in the energy transition. In a nutshell, the model optimises the design of the system by computing the installed capacity of each technology as well as the operation in each period to meet the energy demand and minimise the total annual cost – or the total emissions – of the system. It belongs in the “snapshot” category, as it models only one target year resorting to typical days (TDs) (*Typical days* are “a well-chosen set of historical days to represent an entire year” [45]). As an alternative to TS, TDs can be seen as the next step on the path towards full time series [141]). specifically, EnergyScope adopts a chronological TDs representation: each day of the year is optimally allocated to

its corresponding TD to form a 365-day sequence, which allows the integration of daily and seasonal storage by implementing the formulation recently proposed by Gabrielli et al. [142].

With respect to the previously listed criteria, (i) EnergyScope is open-source (<https://github.com/energyscope/EnergyScope>): the code can be run out-of-the-box, using the data for the Swiss energy system as an example (see Limpens et al. [1]); (ii) it optimises the design and operation of a national energy system accounting for all the energy carriers, sectors and end-use demand types; (iii) it has an hourly resolution, which allows accounting for seasonality and daily/seasonal energy storage; (v) it is a snapshot (S) model; (vi) thanks to the use of TDs, it is computationally efficient, as it runs in ~ 1 minute on a standard PC, which is appropriate for “what-if” analyses and uncertainty applications.

However, as highlighted by Limpens et al. [1], it lacks one of the critical features shown in Table 3, that is (iv) a high spatial resolution allowing to consider, for instance, a zonal definition of energy demands, availability of resources and capacity of RESs. Furthermore, the EnergyScope’s list of end-use demands, resources and technologies options can be widened in order to offer a more detailed representation of future low-carbon energy systems.

3.2. Modelling framework: regionalisation and new features

In this paper, we propose a modified, regionalised version of the EnergyScope model. Concretely, we divide the investigated energy system into a number of geographical regions that can exchange with each other and extend the model by adding energy sectors (*e.g.*, cooling, farming, etc.) and technology options. Figure 1 shows the conceptual structure of the resulting regionalised modelling framework, consisting of three main components: *resources*, *energy conversion technologies* and *demand*.

Given as input the end-use energy demands, the main technical and economic characteristics of the energy conversion technologies, the availability and the cost of the energy resources, the model identifies the optimal energy conversion strategy in order to meet the demand and minimise the objective (total cost or emissions) subject to energy balance and other constraints representing typical restrictions of real-world energy systems (*e.g.* available resources and capacities, operations of technologies and storage, etc.).

Figure 1: Conceptual representation of a regionally-characterised national energy system: *resources* are converted by *technologies* to supply end-use *demand* in the different sectors (electricity, mobility, heating). *Layers* – such as electricity and LT heat – are defined as all the vectors in the system that need to be balanced in each period. The novel features of the regionalised EnergyScope version are highlighted in orange. Abbreviations: natural gas (NG), Internal Combustion Engine (ICE), photovoltaic (PV), low temperature (LT), end-use type (EUT).

In the following, we introduce the regionalised formulation by reporting the key constraints; additional constraints are reported in Appendix A. Besides an expanded input dataset (details at the end of the Section), the differences between this formulation and the one in [1] are the addition of the regionalisation constraints (Eqs. 10 and 11) and the modification of the other constraints (e.g. Eq. 12) to account for exchanges across regions.

Objective function: cost, emissions

The total cost (C_{tot}) (1) is defined as the sum of the energy-related cost at a regional scale ($C_{\text{tot},r}$). The latter is defined as the sum of the annualised investment and operation and maintenance (O&M) cost (C_{maint}) of technologies ($TECH$), and the operating cost (C_{op})

of resources (RES) in each region (2). The total investment cost (\mathbf{C}_{inv}) of each technology results from the multiplication of its specific investment cost (c_{inv}) and installed size (\mathbf{F}) (4). \mathbf{C}_{inv} is annualized with the factor τ , calculated based on the interest rate (i_{rate}) and the technology lifetime (n) (3). The total O&M cost is calculated in the same way (5). The total cost of resources is calculated as the sum of the use ($\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{t}}$) over different hours (h) and typical days (td) multiplied by the period duration (t_{op}) and the specific cost of the resource (c_{op}) (6).

$$\min \quad \mathbf{C}_{\text{tot}} = \sum_{r \in REG} \mathbf{C}_{\text{tot},r}(r) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \mathbf{C}_{\text{tot},r}(r) = \sum_{i \in TECH} (\tau(i)\mathbf{C}_{\text{inv}}(i,r) + \mathbf{C}_{\text{maint}}(i,r)) + \sum_{j \in RES} \mathbf{C}_{\text{op}}(j,r) \quad \forall r \in REG \quad (2)$$

$$\tau(i) = \frac{i_{\text{rate}}(i_{\text{rate}} + 1)^{n(i)}}{(i_{\text{rate}} + 1)^{n(i)} - 1} \quad \forall i \in TECH \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_{\text{inv}}(i,r) = c_{\text{inv}}(i)\mathbf{F}(i,r) \quad \forall i \in TECH, r \in REG \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_{\text{maint}}(i,r) = c_{\text{maint}}(i)\mathbf{F}(i,r) \quad \forall i \in TECH, r \in REG \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_{\text{op}}(j,r) = \sum_{t \in T | (h,td) \in T_H_TD(t)} c_{\text{op}}(j)\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{t}}(j,h,td,r)t_{\text{op}}(h,td) \quad \forall j \in RES, r \in REG \quad (6)$$

The total annual GHG emissions of the system, which can be used as an alternative objective function, are calculated in an equivalent way (Eqs. A.1-A.3).

System design and operation

In the regionalised EnergyScope model, the installed capacity of each technology (\mathbf{F}) with respect to the main output is regionally constrained between an upper (f_{max}) and a lower (f_{min}) bound, respectively (7): f_{min} allows to take into account already existing technologies that will likely be part of the energy system in the future target year (e.g. hydro dams); f_{max}

limits the penetration of those technologies with a regionally constrained potential (e.g. wind turbines or photovoltaic (PV)). The operation of technologies and resources in each period is determined by the decision variable \mathbf{F}_t , as shown in Eqs. (7)-(9), where $c_{p,t}$ is the regionally and hourly defined capacity factor depending on resource availability (e.g. renewables), and $avail$ is the regional yearly availability of resources.

$$f_{min}(i, r) \leq \mathbf{F}(i, r) \leq f_{max}(i, r) \quad \forall i \in TECH, r \in REG \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_t(i, h, td, r) \leq \mathbf{F}(i, r)c_{p,t}(i, h, td, r) \quad \forall i \in TECH, h \in H, td \in TD, r \in REG \quad (8)$$

$$\sum_{t \in T | (h, td) \in T.H.TD(t)} \mathbf{F}_t(j, h, td, r)t_{op}(h, td) \leq avail(j, r) \quad \forall j \in RES, r \in REG \quad (9)$$

Resources allowed to be exchanged from one region (r') to another (r'') are included in the set *EXCHANGE* (*EXCH*). An additional variable (**ship**) is introduced to model exchanges between regions: a positive value of this variable denotes an exchange from r' to r'' ; a negative value denotes an exchange from r'' to r' (10). Exchange of all other resources across regions is forbidden (11).

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{ship}(l, h, td, r', r'') &= -\mathbf{ship}(l, h, td, r'', r') \\ \forall l \in L, h \in H, td \in TD, r' \in REG, r'' \in REG | r' \neq r'' \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{ship}(l, h, td, r', r'') = 0 \quad \forall l \in L \setminus EXCH, h \in H, td \in TD, r' \in REG, r'' \in REG | r' \neq r'' \quad (11)$$

Eq. (12) is the main energy and resource balance constraint: *layers* are defined as all the vectors in the system that need to be balanced in each period, such as resources and end-use demand (EUD). The efficiency matrix f defines for all technologies and resources outputs to (positive) and inputs from (negative) layers. Eq. (12) expresses the balance for each layer l : all outputs from resources and technologies (including storage and imports from other

regions) are used to either satisfy the EUD, as inputs to other resources and technologies, or are exported to other regions.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{j \in RES \cup TECH \setminus STO} f(j, l) \mathbf{F}_t(j, h, td, r) + \sum_{i \in STO} (\mathbf{Sto}_{out}(i, l, h, td, r) - \mathbf{Sto}_{in}(i, l, h, td, r)) \\
& - \mathbf{EndUses}(l, h, td, r) - \sum_{r'' \in REG | r'' \neq r} \mathbf{ship}(l, h, td, r, r'') = 0 \quad (12) \\
& \forall l \in L, h \in H, td \in TD, r \in REG
\end{aligned}$$

Storage

The framework allows to model daily as well as seasonal storage. For storage technologies, the level of stored energy (\mathbf{Sto}_{level}) at time t is equal to the level at time $t - 1$ plus inputs minus outputs, considering input/output efficiencies ($\eta_{sto,in}$, $\eta_{sto,out}$) and storage losses ($\%sto_{loss}$) (13). Finally, Eq. (14) limits the input/output energy flows considering the installed size of storage technologies, their availability ($\%sto_{avail}$) and both the related charging ($t_{sto,in}$) and discharging ($t_{sto,out}$) times, defined as the time needed to complete a full charge/discharge from empty/full storage.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathbf{Sto}_{level}(i, t, r) = \mathbf{Sto}_{level}(i, t - 1, r) \cdot (1 - \%sto_{loss}(i)) \\
& + t_{op}(h, td) \cdot \left(\sum_{l \in L | \eta_{sto,in}(i,l) > 0} \mathbf{Sto}_{in}(i, l, h, td, r) \eta_{sto,in}(i, l) - \sum_{l \in L | \eta_{sto,out}(i,l) > 0} \mathbf{Sto}_{out}(i, l, h, td, r) / \eta_{sto,out}(i, l) \right) \quad (13) \\
& \forall i \in STO, t \in T, (h, td) \in T_H_TD(t), r \in REG
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& (\mathbf{Sto}_{in}(i, l, h, td, r) t_{sto,in}(i) + \mathbf{Sto}_{out}(i, l, h, td, r) t_{sto,out}(i)) \cdot t_{op}(h, td) \leq \mathbf{F}(i, r) \%sto_{avail}(i) \\
& \forall i \in STO, l \in L, h \in H, td \in TD, r \in REG \quad (14)
\end{aligned}$$

Additional constraints & technologies

Additional constraints are added to account for the extra investments needed in the context of the energy transition. As an example, we account for an additional investment cost for the electricity grid as a result of the integration of intermittent RESs such as wind

and solar, as well as for additional investments in safety and adequacy due to the scheduled phase-out of coal power plants (all data are reported in the Supplementary Material).

Furthermore, with respect to previous works adopting this modelling framework, our regionalised version includes additional sectors and technology options: (i) demand due to cooling (for both space cooling and industrial processes) and machinery needed for farming; (ii) non-woody biomass conversion options such as biogas and biomass for electricity (i.e. bioliquid); (iii) additional technologies for mobility, electricity generation, cooling and heat production (Figure B.7 illustrates all the modelled energy conversion options for the Italian case study).

4. Case-study: the Italian energy transition

As a case study, we apply the model to the Italian national energy system. First, a brief overview of the Italian context is provided; then, we devise a possible deep decarbonisation pathway towards a 100% RE Italian energy system for the year 2050. For this deterministic (*i.e.*, not accounting for uncertainty) scenario, we present the main results in terms of general trends, electrification and sector-coupling, penetration of RESs and storage technologies. Additionally, we evaluate to which extent uncertainties in the deployment of carbon capture and storage (CCS) and renewable technologies can hinder the attainment of Italy’s decarbonisation targets. According to our review in Section 2.2 and to the best of our knowledge, this is the first open-source model of the Italian energy system including all the energy sectors (electricity, heating and mobility).

4.1. Italian climate policies and modelling approach

In order to meet – and possibly overcome – the ambitious 80% emissions target set by the EU for 2050 [5], Italy has planned several actions aiming at partially-to-fully decarbonising its energy system (“Proposta di Piano Nazionale Integrato per l’Energia e il Clima” [143] and “National Energy Strategy (NES) 2017” [144]). The Country’s aim is not only to decarbonise, but also to modernise and innovate in a less carbon- and resource-intensive direction. In this context, the energy transition of the Italian energy system is likely to be significantly affected

by: (i) a high penetration of RESs such as wind and solar PV, the availability of which is strongly regionally dependent; (ii) R&D efforts in storage technologies and CCS, able to compensate the variability of RESs and to reduce the environmental impact of conventional power plants; (iii) a modernisation of the electricity grid in terms of security and adequacy, to handle both the increasing intermittent electricity generation from RESs and the the increasing penetration of e-mobility and heat pumps; (iv) investments on modern energy conversion technologies to increase energy efficiency in all sectors.

In view of these challenges, the regionalised EnergyScope modelling framework presented in Section 3.2 is applied to the Italian energy system to assess these dynamics. First, to verify accuracy and consistency, the model is used to represent the current state of the system: concretely, we assess whether the model can reproduce the state of the Italian energy system in the year 2015 (data, methodology and results reported in Appendix B and in the Supplementary Material). Then, in the following, we project the Italian energy system to the year 2050 to devise a deep decarbonisation scenario.

4.2. A deep decarbonisation scenario for the Italian energy system

In this section, the model is applied to assess the maximum deep decarbonisation potential for the Italian energy system in 2050, maximising as well RE penetration. Projected values for the key input parameters – such as fuel and resource prices, EUD and technologies development status – are taken from different forecasts. Specifically, the Italian yearly EUD projections used as input parameters in EnergyScope are estimated based on EU reports (such as [145] and [146]), which offer energy demand trends for Italy until 2050); commodity and technology price forecasts are instead based on specific scenario studies for Italy (e.g. [147] and [71]), while regional technical potentials of RESs are calculated starting from national values by Colbertaldo et al. [36] (Appendix B.2). For the emissions, we consider only direct CO₂ emissions from fuel combustion [148]. All other data sources and assumptions are reported in detail in the Supplementary Material.

Under the modelling approach perspective, we perform our study using 12 TDs, which offers a good trade-off between accuracy and computational time as discussed by Limpens

et al. [1]. For the same reason, under the spatial resolution aspect, we subdivide the Italian national energy system into three macro-regions: North (Piemonte, Valle d’Aosta, Liguria, Lombardia, Trentino Alto Adige, Veneto, Friuli Venezia Giulia and Emilia Romagna), Centre (Toscana, Umbria, Marche, Lazio, Campania and Abruzzo), South (Molise, Puglia, Basilicata, Calabria and the two major islands, Sardegna and Sicilia). This repartition ensures (i) an appropriate spatial detail without significantly increasing the computational time (~ 4 mins, see Table 4), as well as (ii) a good availability and degree of detail of input data. In fact, while time series and few other parameters are available at a higher degree of detail (up to six macro-regions), for the majority of the other data – in particular, for heating and mobility – increasing the level of detail would require making strong assumptions (due to unavailability of data), hence affecting the accuracy of the model’s outputs.

Table 4: Application of the regionalised EnergyScope model to the Italian energy system: spatial resolution (number of regions) vs. computational time using the commercial software IBM CPLEX 12.9 on a standard laptop (Intel Core i7 2.7 GHz, with 4 cores and 16GB of RAM).

# of Regions	Computational Time [s]
1	76
2	115
3	250
4	664
5	970

Each region is characterised by its own energy demand, renewable potential and biomass availability. Only inter-regional exchanges of electricity are allowed, while electricity imports are only allowed for the Northern region, which historically mostly imported from Switzerland, France and Slovenia [147]; additionally, import of fossil resources is assumed to be potentially unlimited on a regional scale, whereas local resources (e.g. biomass) are constrained by specific macro-regional availabilities and must be exploited within the corresponding regional boundaries.

4.3. Results

The Sankey diagram in Figure 2 illustrates the main energy flows for this 2050 deterministic deep decarbonisation scenario, aiming at reducing GHG emissions while maximising RE penetration. The diagram represents the entire energy conversion chain, from resources to end-use demand, providing a global representation of the Italian energy system towards a nearly-zero carbon emissions configuration.

The Figure shows that Italy can reach a near-zero carbon emissions configuration by 2050 emitting 9.5 MtCO₂/y, which corresponds to a 97% reduction compared to 1990 levels. In this scenario, fossil emissions come from natural gas (NG) (1.58 MtCO₂/y) – used in combined cycle gas turbine (CCGT) power plants with CCS (90% capture rate) – from diesel (1.36 MtCO₂/y), used for freight and public mobility, and from municipal solid waste (6.55 MtCO₂/y).

The main factors enabling this transition are: a wide electrification of the system; a larger penetration of RES; an increased penetration of more efficient technologies (such as cogeneration, heat pumps and electric mobility) as a result of sector-coupling.

The model uses two levers to minimise emissions and maximise the share of RESs. The first lever is a 44% reduction in total primary energy supply (TPES) compared to the Italian energy system in the year 2015 (Appendix A), passing from 1499 TWh to 841 TWh, as shown in Figure 3a. This reduction is achieved by an increased use of more efficient energy conversion technologies, such as cogeneration of heat and power (CHP), heat pumps (HPs), electric vehicles (EVs) and district heating network (DHN). Overall, this leads to a deep electrification of heating (+61% vs 2015) and mobility (+1300% vs 2015), strongly linking these sectors to the power generation sector (*sector-coupling*, Figure 3b). As a consequence, the power generation sector increases in size (498 TWh/y, +60% compared to 2015), supplied mainly by renewable sources (85% of total power production) and by NG (with CCS, accounting for 9% of total power production). Imported electricity (assumed to be non-fossil due to the expected energy transition in neighbouring countries) accounts for the remaining 6%, as shown in Figure 4a.

Figure 3: a) Italian primary energy consumption by source in 2015 and 2050; b) Penetration of electricity in the heating and mobility sectors plus electrolysis (*sector-coupling*).

Fuel shifting from high carbon-intensive fossil fuels (*e.g.*, coal, light fuel oil, etc.) to cleaner fuels (*e.g.*, NG) and local renewable sources, besides strongly reducing emissions, brings as well significant advantages in terms of national energy independence and security of supply. In particular, the share of fossils in TPES in 2015 and 2050 is 79% and 10%, respectively.

The second lever is an increased penetration of RE resources: the overall share of RE in TPES passes from 16% to 83% from 2015 to 2050, out of which 54% are intermittent (especially onshore wind and solar). To face the intermittency problem, sensible thermal energy storage (TES) capacities (hot water tanks) are deployed: 39 and 367 GWh of centralised and decentralised TES capacity, respectively. Furthermore, the generation capacity is affected by the availability of biomethane and of CCS technologies. The latter, which brings a 14.2 MtCO₂/y reduction compared to a scenario without CCS, is still at the development stage and concerns still exist regarding its viability; however, Italy is one of the few countries

Figure 4: a) Italian electricity mix in 2015 and 2050; b) Macro-regional share by source of Italy’s electricity production in 2050 (values in TWh).

where pilot plants have been already deployed. Sensitivity of the results with respect to CCS availability is assessed in the next Section.

In summary, the emission reduction and RE share targets are reached thanks to the nearly complete electrification of heat and mobility (with HPs and EVs, respectively), and to a large penetration of efficient technologies and intermittent RE. In this context, TES is used as a buffer for the electricity grid, which reduces the need for electrical storage. The absence of electrical storage is also a consequence of the high cooling demand (novel implementation in this regionalised EnergyScope model) and of an increased electricity demand for private and public mobility (103.7 TWh), which are both synchronous with PV production profiles.

The total annual cost of the energy system is 109.3 billion $\text{€}_{2015}/\text{y}$, with the annualised investment (CAPEX) and maintenance costs accounting for 78% of the total cost (+124% with respect to 2015); the remaining is the cost of resources that sums to 24.1 billion $\text{€}_{2015}/\text{y}$ (-49.7% with respect to 2015). Focusing on the power sector alone, the modelled deep

decarbonisation scenario leads to an overall 22% cost increase with respect to 2015, reaching 44.6 billion $\text{€}_{2015}/\text{y}$ in 2050. Specifically, the overall costs related with power generation and grid innovation/reinforcement increase by 59% and 12%, respectively. However, given the higher electricity production in 2050 and the lower consumption of resources, the levelised cost of electricity production is significantly reduced compared to 2015 levels (-35%), passing from 147 to 96 $\text{€}/\text{MWh}$ (or, respectively, from 76 to 53 $\text{€}/\text{MWh}$, if not accounting for the fixed investment costs related to the transmission grid).

4.4. *Uncertainty analysis*

The scenario presented in Section 4.3 is characterised by a high penetration of CCS and renewable technologies. In any deep decarbonisation study, the maximum available potential of these new technologies and renewable resources is calculated based on assumptions which are inevitably affected by significant uncertainty.

To address this issue, in this Section we perform an uncertainty analysis to assess the extent to which a lower-than-expected deployment of CCS and renewables can hinder the attainment of the 97% decarbonisation target resulting from our scenario. To do this, we consider three values – low, medium, high – for 7 important input parameters (reported in Table 5) and run our model $3^7 = 2187$ times to evaluate the impact of all the possible permutations of these parameters on the maximum achievable CO_2 reduction, which we set as the objective function in these runs.

The results are summarised by the boxplot in Figure 5. In the best case scenario, all the resources and technologies can be exploited up to their “high” potential (as in the deterministic scenario in the previous Section) and hence, as expected, emissions reach 9.2 MtCO_2/y , –97.5% compared to 1990 emission levels. In the worst-case scenario, corresponding to an assumed low availability of all the considered resources and technologies, the maximum attainable level of CO_2 emissions is 76.3 MtCO_2/y , –79.3% compared to 1990 emission levels. All the other scenarios lie in between these two extremes, with 50% of the scenarios below 40.5 MtCO_2/y .

Table 5: Low and high potential for CCS and renewable technologies in the year 2050 used as input for the uncertainty analysis. Sources for “low” values are reported in the Table. “High” values are the values used in the deterministic model. “Medium” values are taken as the average of “low” and “high” values.

Parameter	Units	2050 Potential (Low)			2050 Potential (High)		
		North	Centre	South	North	Centre	South
CCS (NG)	[GW]	0.7 ^a	0.7 ^a	0.7 ^a	2	2	2
CCS (Coal)	[GW]	0 ^a	0 ^a	0 ^a	1.5	1.5	1.5
PV	[GW]	25.0 ^b	15.3 ^b	16.5 ^b	48.4	29.7	31.9
Wind Onshore	[GW]	0.33 ^b	6.05 ^b	19.6 ^b	0.62	11.4	37.0
Wind Offshore	[GW]	0	0	0.5 ^c	0	0	1.5
Wood	[GWh/y]	14110 ^d	8039 ^d	1968 ^d	43436	24864	22333
Biogas	[GWh/y]	32089 ^c	4011 ^c	4011 ^c	79781	9973	9973

^a From Viridis [59]

^b From Capros et al. [145]

^c Assumption.

^d Equal to 2015 data.

Figure 5: Boxplot reporting the distribution of the objective function (CO₂ emission reduction) across the $3^7 = 2187$ runs of the uncertainty analysis. In the worst-case scenario, emissions can be reduced by 79.3% compared to 1990 levels. In the best-case scenario, using the same assumption as in the deterministic model, emissions can reach a 97.5% reduction compared to 1990 levels.

5. Discussion

5.1. Advantages and limitations of the proposed modelling framework

The application to the Italian case study demonstrates that the proposed modelling framework is suitable for assessing deep decarbonisation scenarios for regionally characterised large-scale energy systems. With respect to the review criteria defined in Section 2, this framework has the advantages of being open-source, of optimising both investments and operation, and of offering a good spatial and temporal resolution with a low computational time, which make the model suitable for uncertainty and *what-if* analyses.

In particular, with respect to the EnergyScope model version presented by Limpens et al. [1], this regionalised version allows to: (i) characterise with a higher level of detail the energy demand (e.g. in the case of Italy, industrial heat demand is 75.6 TWh in the North, 39.5 TWh in the Centre and 16.4 TWh in the South), the time series, the capacity factors of renewables (e.g. the average capacity factor for onshore wind in 2050 is estimated to be 20% in the North and 30% in the South [71]) and the availability of local resources; (ii) evaluate where intermittent renewable energies (iRE) are more likely to be deployed (in our case study, 52% of iRE production is in the South, 24% in both the Centre and the North, Figure 4b) in order to plan for flexibility infrastructures and power grid investments to manage overproduction and risks of congestion; (iii) define realistic limits for the penetration of specific resources and technologies, accounting for climatic reasons (e.g. we impose that DHN cannot be used in the South), geography (e.g. spatial location of wind and geothermal resources) and other factors (e.g. biomethane availability in the North due to the large presence of wet biomass from agriculture and breeding). This higher resolution comes with an associated moderately increased computational cost: the regionalised EnergyScope model solves in approximately 4 mins on a standard computer, vs 1 min of the 1-region case.

In line with other recent studies [149], our results confirm that cross-sectoral synergies – e.g. heat pumps and electric vehicles, or vehicle-to-grid and thermal storage acting as buffers for the electricity grid – are key enablers for the energy transition. In this context, evaluating technologies “in isolation” or focusing solely on one sector might lead to suboptimal solutions.

A *whole-energy system* modelling approach like the one we propose is crucial in order to capture such dynamics [9]. This is an emerging trend: 44 out of the 88 studies in Table 2 adopt a whole-energy system approach, while the remaining focus solely on one or two sectors (29 focus on the electricity sector). Out of the 29 different modelling frameworks adopted across the 88 studies, 10 offer a whole-energy modelling approach (Table 3).

Importantly, our analysis accounts for some of the fundamental uncertainties impacting the energy transition, such as the deployment of CCS and renewables, showing that Italy can achieve very high emission reduction targets even under lower-than-expected deployment of key technologies. In this context, while most energy models are *deterministic*, the recent literature has proven that uncertainty can dramatically affect the outcome of energy models [150], and various methods have been proposed to integrate uncertainty in energy studies [151]. Similarly to increasing the level of detail, integrating uncertainty also negatively affects computational tractability. By keeping computational times in check, our model enables a systematic consideration of uncertainty in deep decarbonisation studies.

There are, however, some limitations, as well as applications for which the model is not designed for. First, in the context of deep decarbonisation studies, the model represents the transmission grid in a rather simplified way, which does not allow for an assessment of transmission reliability and congestion risks. Our results for the Italian case-study in 2050 (Section 4.3) – such as (i) the expected large power flows from regions with high RE penetration and low demand (e.g. South) to regions with low RE potential and high demand (e.g. North) and (ii) the high penetration of iRE – call for closer attention to these aspects. To carry out such analyses, our framework could be coupled to dedicated grid modelling tools such as PyPSA [152] and Dispa-SET [153]; additional insights could be gained by comparing the EnergyScope results to the outputs of models like Calliope [104], which focus on the electricity sector and hence are more detailed in modelling the transmission grid.

Second, EnergyScope models a future target year (*snapshot* approach), and thus cannot directly account for the transition pathway to implement the devised decarbonisation strat-

egy. In this context, other open-source *pathway* optimisation models, such as OSeMOSYS, would be a suitable complement.

Third, the model could be extended by adding other sectors (e.g. aviation and maritime transport), as well as additional data regarding the economic impact of transportation infrastructure (e.g. railways), investments on trains for freight and on public/private means of transport.

5.2. Which model should you use?

Choosing among the wide range of available energy models can be overwhelming. In this context, given the wide availability and increasing quality of energy models, building on existing and consolidated frameworks can be beneficial over developing new case-specific models from scratch, unless facing specific needs which current models are unable to appropriately capture.

In this work, we have proposed a modelling framework which can help addressing some of the key challenges linked to deep decarbonisation. In particular, thanks to a low computational time and a concise formulation, the proposed framework is suitable for the development uncertainty and *what-if* analyses. However, our analysis has also confirmed that there is no *one-size-fits-all* for energy models – the energy transition is a complex and interdisciplinary phenomenon, where different models can answer different questions and it is unlikely that a single modelling framework will ever be able to capture all these relevant and interlinked dynamics. In this context, coupling different models can be a promising avenue, as we discussed in the previous Section by considering options for coupling EnergyScope with PyPSA, Dispa-SET, Calliope and OSeMOSYS. Model coupling can be performed in two ways : i) *soft-linking* models by running them in sequence, e.g. using the output of a strategic planning model as input of a transmission grid modelling tool; ii) comparing two similar models for the same case study (aligning their assumptions), which can provide very helpful insights for policy-making and could also result in an effective debugging solution.

6. Conclusion

In the context of the energy transition, an increasing number of studies propose pathways for the deep decarbonisation of national/regional energy systems adopting a large variety of energy modelling frameworks. In this paper, we introduce a novel modelling approach, consisting of a regionalised version of the EnergyScope model [10, 1], which is particularly suitable for uncertainty and *what-if* analyses and could complement more detailed and established energy models optimising the energy transition pathway. Salient features of the proposed model are open-source availability, a *snapshot* approach (i.e., modelling a target-year in the future), a concise formulation and a low computational time. By critically comparing our model to other models used across 88 recent deep decarbonisation studies, we discuss the advantages and limitations of our model in context of the quickly developing energy modelling panorama.

As a case study, we apply the model to Italy and present the first open-source model of the Italian energy system including all the energy sectors (electricity, heating and mobility). Our analysis proposes a possible near-zero CO₂ emissions scenario for Italy in 2050, reaching 9.5 MtCO₂/y (-97% with respect to 1990 levels) thanks to a radical electrification of the energy system coupled with a wide deployment of renewables and efficient energy conversion technologies (such as heat pumps and electric vehicles, among others). We further assess the feasibility of Italy’s decarbonisation strategy with respect to uncertainties in the deployment of CCS and renewable technologies, showing that under all considered scenarios emissions can be reduced by 79-97%. Future work will focus on the addition of new energy conversion options to the model as well as on a more refined modelling of the transmission grid to assess the feasibility of the proposed scenario.

Data availability

Source code and data (including documentation of sources) are available at <https://zenodo.org/record/5482657> [11] and in the Supplementary Material. The Italy EnergyScope model repository can be found at <https://github.com/energyscope/EnergyScope/>

tree/EnergyScopeIT, where new versions will be released.

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Author Contribution statement

MB and SM contributed equally as first-authors to all stages of this work. MB was responsible for data collection and analysis of the literature. SM was responsible for the uncertainty analysis.

Appendix A. LP model formulation

The conceptual energy system structure described in Figure 1 is mathematically formulated as a LP problem. This Section extends and complete the set of constraints introduced in Section 3.2.

Appendix A.1. End-use demand

Figure A.6 shows the constraints relative to the calculation of the regional hourly end-uses demand (**EndUses**), which are computed starting from the normalised hourly time series and yearly EUD values given as input (*endUsesInput*). With respect to Limpens et al. [1], three new **EndUses** types are added: farming mobility, cooling for industrial processes, space cooling. Electricity end-use is the combination of two different energy demands: lighting, variable according to $\%_{elec}$, and electrical appliances, which is assumed to be constant over the year. Low temperature heat for hot water production, heating and cooling for processes and mobility farming are also evenly distributed over the year. On the contrary, regional space heating and cooling demand, passenger and freight mobility are distributed over the year according to $\%_{sh}$, $\%_{sc}$, $\%_{pass}$ and $\%_{fr}$, respectively. The regional repartition between centralised (DHN) and decentralised heat is modelled according to the independent decision variable $\%_{DHN}$. The same applies for the percentage of public transportation vs private mobility, defined by $\%_{Public}$, and for the percentage of trains over freight mobility, defined by $\%_{Rail}$. Finally, for both electricity and centralised low temperature heat demands, grid/network losses are taken into account with the dependent variable **Net_{losses}**. The obtained hourly demand profiles are clustered into typical days following the methodology defined by Limpens et al. [1].

Appendix A.2. Emissions

Similarly to **C_{tot}**, the total annual GHG emissions of the system (**GWP_{tot}**) (A.1) are defined as the sum of the energy-related GHG emissions at a regional scale (**GWP_{tot,r}**, A.2). The latter are defined as the sum of the operating emissions from combustion of resources (**GWP_{op}**) in each region, taking into account the specific emission factors (*gwp_{op}*) (A.3).

Figure A.6: **EndUses** calculation starting from *endUsesInput*. Abbreviations: space heating (sh), space cooling (sc), process (pro), district heating network (DHN), hot water (HW), passenger (pass) and freight (fr). Adapted from Limpens et al. [1].

$$\mathbf{GWP}_{\text{tot}} = \sum_{r \in REG} \mathbf{GWP}_{\text{tot},r}(r) \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$\mathbf{GWP}_{\text{tot},r}(r) = \sum_{j \in RES} \mathbf{GWP}_{\text{op}}(j, r) \quad \forall r \in REG \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$\mathbf{GWP}_{\text{op}}(j, r) = \sum_{t \in T | (h, td) \in T.H.TD(t)} gwp_{op}(j) \mathbf{F}_t(j, h, td, r) t_{op}(h, td) \quad \forall j \in RES, r \in REG \quad (\text{A.3})$$

\mathbf{C}_{tot} and $\mathbf{GWP}_{\text{tot}}$ can alternatively be used as the objective function of our LP model. In this paper (with the exception of the uncertainty analysis), we use \mathbf{C}_{tot} as the objective function to be minimised, and constrain $\mathbf{GWP}_{\text{tot}}$ to be lower or equal than an upper bound (gwp_{limit}).

Appendix A.3. Additional constraints

We introduce additional equations to model the investments needed for the deep decarbonisation of national energy systems. As in Limpens et al. [1], (A.4) allows to define an

additional investment cost for the electricity grid ($c_{grid,extra}$) proportional to the penetration of intermittent RES such as wind and solar. Additionally, (A.5), specific to the Italian case, considers the total additional investments in safety and adequacy of the electric grid due to the scheduled phase-out of coal power plants by 2025 [143].

$$\mathbf{F}(Grid, r) = \frac{c_{grid,extra}}{c_{inv}(Grid)} \frac{\mathbf{F}(Wind, r) + \mathbf{F}(PV, r)}{f_{max}(Wind, r) + f_{max}(PV, r)} \quad \forall r \in REG \quad (A.4)$$

$$\mathbf{F}(Grid_Coal, r) = 1 - \frac{\mathbf{F}(Coal_US, r)}{f_{max}(Coal_US, r)} \quad \forall r \in REG \quad (A.5)$$

Appendix B. Application of EnergyScope to the Italian energy system

Figure B.7 illustrates the application of EnergyScope to the Italian case study. The multi-vector multi-sector model includes: renewable and fossil resources; already-available and promising energy conversion technologies; different types of end-use demand. Overall, the model includes 29 layers, 11 end-use demand types and 106 technologies.

Appendix B.1. Demonstration for the year 2015

Long-term planning models are fundamentally non-validatable since they model the future configuration of national energy systems [154]. However, in order to verify the accuracy of the formulation and the consistency of results, such models can be used to represent a known state of the system (past or current). To do this, we assess whether the model can reproduce the state of the Italian energy system in the year 2015. This year has been chosen for the two following reasons: (i) 2015 is taken as a reference year for multiple European reports [146] and national directives [144]; (ii) the good availability of detailed data collected from online databases of public research bodies, national operators and European associations.

The LP model described in Section 3.2 is run with the 2015 data and constraints reported in detail in the Supplementary Material. The Sankey diagram in Figure B.8 illustrates the main energy flows of the resulting configuration for the year 2015. The corresponding numerical results are reported in Table B.6, where we compare the model outputs with the

Figure B.7: Application of the LP modelling framework to the Italian energy system. Abbreviations: natural gas (NG), carbon capture and storage (CCS), synthetic natural gas (SNG), geothermal (geoth.) combined cycle gas turbine (CCGT), integrated gasification combined cycle (IGCC), photovoltaic (PV), temperature (T), plug-in hybrid electric vehicle (PHEV), cogeneration of heat and power (CHP), biomass for electricity generation (Bio. Elec), pressure swing adsorption (PSA).

reported values for the year 2015 based on the following two indicators: (i) primary energy consumption, global and per type of fuel; (ii) global GHG emissions.

Figure B.8: Application of EnergyScope to Italy: energy flows for the year 2015. All values are in TWh.

In terms of energy consumption, the LP model approximates well the real-world Italian energy system in 2015. The main differences with respect to the actual values are due to the following assumptions: i) the electricity from CHP plants is underestimated since the model does not account for the actual alternation between cogenerative and non-cogenerative mode of production (the latter is not considered). As a consequence, in order to fill this production gap, the model overestimates the amount of imported electricity. ii) The contribution of some types of biomass classified as “Biomass for Elec.” in [155] and other contributions from fossil fuels (such as coal by-products and half-processed oils) explain other small differences between the model outputs and the actual 2015 values.

In terms of emissions, the actual energy related emissions from fuel combustion in 2015 are estimated to be 305.04 MtCO₂/y [159], not including the contribution of fugitive emissions

Table B.6: Model validation: model outputs vs. actual 2015 values for the Italian energy system. Actual values for the Italian energy system are taken from [155] unless otherwise indicated.

		Actual 2015	LP	Δ	Δ_{rel}	Units
Primary Energy Consumption	Gasoline	95.24	97.65	2.41	2.53 %	TWh
	Diesel	302.06	300.77	-1.28	-0.42 %	TWh
	- Diesel for Mobility	280.17	291.05	10.88	3.88 %	TWh
	Light Fuel Oil	14.86	14.80	-0.07	-0.46 %	TWh
	Coal	144.29	145.89	1.60	1.11 %	TWh
	- Coal for Elec.	114.00	111.98	-2.02	-1.77 %	TWh
	NG	617.39	623.59	6.20	1.00 %	TWh
	- NG for Mobility	31.56	31.25	-0.31	-0.99 %	TWh
	- NG for Elec.	196.24	191.96	-4.28	-2.18 %	TWh
	Elec. Imports	50.80	63.00	12.92	24.02 %	TWh
	Solar & Wind^a	37.79	37.79	0.0	0.0 %	TWh
	Geothermal^a	6.19	6.10	-0.09	-1.44 %	TWh
	Waste	17.16	17.11	-0.05	-0.28 %	TWh
	Wood	76.52	78.76	2.24	2.92 %	TWh
	Biomass for Elec.	42.25	46.51	4.26	10.08 %	TWh
	- Biogas ^b	22.81	22.19	-0.62	-2.68 %	TWh
Global	1464.35	1498.89	34.54	2.36 %	TWh	
Technologies	DHN	10.49 ^c	10.94	0.45	4.28 %	TWh
CO₂ emissions (Fossil)		305.04 ^d	289.53	-15.51	-5.08 %	MtCO ₂

^aData for renewable primary energy consumption are reported from [155] and from [156].

^bFrom [157].

^cFrom Table 9 in [158].

^dFrom Table 1 (s1-s2) in [159]. Emissions of CO₂ are evaluated considering only energy-related emissions and removing fugitive emissions from fuels (aviation and maritime transport excluded).

from fuels and the impact of internal navigation and maritime transport (which are not accounted for in our model). This number is estimated well by the regionalised EnergyScope model. Also in this case, the difference is mainly due to the overestimation of imported electricity [148].

Appendix B.2. Renewable Energy Potential

The energy transition relies on RESs; as such, their deployment potential is a critical parameter in order to evaluate long-term low-carbon scenarios. Table B.7 reports the regional installed capacity in 2015 (based on our results) and the specific maximum available capacity (f_{max}) for each RES considered in the regionalised Energyscope formulation for the year 2050. f_{max} values are regionally calculated starting from national data from Colbertaldo et al. [36], scaled according to the regional production share of each technology in 2015 from [156]. Wind, solar, hydro, geothermal and biomass are foreseen to be the main resources: the additional potential of hydro is very limited and almost fully exploited; the technical potentials of PV and wind are deduced from Colbertaldo et al. [36]; regional values for PHES in 2015 are provided from Colbertaldo et al. [36] while the f_{max} values for 2050 are assumed to be equal to the maximum electricity production from pumped storage ever performed in Italy in the last 20 years (i.e. in the year 2002 [147]).

Table B.7: Regional installed capacity in 2015 and maximum potential for each RES considered in the EnergyScope model formulation in 2050.

Technology	2015 [GW]			$f_{max,2050}$ [GW]		
	NO	CN	SO	NO	CN	SO
Solar PV	8.3	5.1	5.4	48.4	29.6	31.9
CSP	0	0	0	0	0	0.3 ^a
Wave	0	0	0	0	0	0.3 ^a
Onshore Wind	0.1	2.1	6.9	0.6	11.4	36.9
Offshore Wind ^b	0	0	0	0	0	1.5
Hydro Dam	8.4	1.9	1.6	8.8 ^c	2.0 ^c	1.7 ^c
Hydro River	7.9	1.0	1.2	8.3 ^c	1.1 ^c	1.3 ^c
Geothermal	0	0.8	0	0	1	0
Geothermal ORC	0	0	0	0.3	0.3	0.3
PHES ^d	762	317	310	5285	1482	841

^aIt is assumed that the potential development of CSP and of wave energy would be possible only in the South of Italy for geographical and climatic reasons.

^bThe technical potential of off-shore wind turbines is limited by the structure of the Italian coastline; it is assumed based on [36].

^cIn 2050 a 5% increase is assumed according to forecasts from [145].

^dReported values are in GWh from [147].

References

- [1] Limpens, G., Moret, S., Jeanmart, H., Maréchal, F.. EnergyScope TD: A novel open-source model for regional energy systems. *Applied Energy* 2019;255:113729. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306261919314163>. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.113729.
- [2] Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), . Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Tech. Rep.; 2021.
- [3] Thompson, L.G.. Climate Change: The Evidence and Our Options. *The Behavior Analyst* 2010;33(2):153–170. URL: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2995507/>.
- [4] The Paris Agreement | UNFCCC. 2015. URL: <https://unfccc.int/process-and-meetings/the-paris-agreement/the-paris-agreement>.
- [5] Commission, E., editor. Energy roadmap 2050. Energy; Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union; 2012. ISBN 978-92-79-21798-2. OCLC: ocn778704609.
- [6] A European Green Deal. 2019. URL: https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en; library Catalog: ec.europa.eu.
- [7] IRENA - Energy Transition. 2019. URL: <https://www.irena.org/energytransition>.
- [8] Pfenninger, S., Hawkes, A., Keirstead, J.. Energy systems modeling for twenty-first century energy challenges. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2014;33:74–86. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032114000872>. doi:10.1016/j.rser.2014.02.003.

- [9] Contino, F., Moret, S., Limpens, G., Jeanmart, H.. Whole-energy system models: The advisors for the energy transition. *Progress in Energy and Combustion Science* 2020;81:100872. doi:10.1016/j.pecs.2020.100872.
- [10] Moret, S.. Strategic energy planning under uncertainty. Doctoral Thesis; EPFL; 2017. URL: <https://www.research-collection.ethz.ch/handle/20.500.11850/71958>. doi:10.5075/epfl-thesis-7961.
- [11] Moret, S.. Energyscope/EnergyScope: Borasio_deep_2021_code. Zenodo; 2021. doi:10.5281/zenodo.5482657.
- [12] Deason, W.. Comparison of 100% renewable energy system scenarios with a focus on flexibility and cost. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2018;82:3168–3178. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032117313990>. doi:10.1016/j.rser.2017.10.026.
- [13] Limpens, G., Jeanmart, H., Maréchal, F.. Belgian Energy Transition: What Are the Options? *Energies* 2020;13(1):261. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/13/1/261>. doi:10.3390/en13010261.
- [14] Hall, L.M.H., Buckley, A.R.. A review of energy systems models in the UK: Prevalent usage and categorisation. *Applied Energy* 2016;169:607–628. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.02.044.
- [15] Connolly, D., Lund, H., Mathiesen, B.V., Leahy, M.. The first step towards a 100% renewable energy-system for Ireland. *Applied Energy* 2011;88(2):502–507. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S030626191000070X>. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2010.03.006.
- [16] Child, M., Breyer, C.. Vision and initial feasibility analysis of a recarbonised Finnish energy system for 2050. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2016;66:517–536. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032116303306>. doi:10.1016/j.rser.2016.07.001.

- [17] Lund, H., Mathiesen, B.V.. Energy system analysis of 100% renewable energy systems—The case of Denmark in years 2030 and 2050. *Energy* 2009;34(5):524–531. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544208000959>. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2008.04.003.
- [18] Čosić, B., Krajačić, G., Duić, N.. A 100% renewable energy system in the year 2050: The case of Macedonia. *Energy* 2012;48(1):80–87. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544212005300>. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2012.06.078.
- [19] Fernandes, L., Ferreira, P.. Renewable energy scenarios in the Portuguese electricity system. *Energy* 2014;69:51–57. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S036054421400245X>. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2014.02.098.
- [20] Calise, F., D’Accadia, M.D., Barletta, C., Battaglia, V., Pfeifer, A., Duić, N.. Detailed Modelling of the Deep Decarbonisation Scenarios with Demand Response Technologies in the Heating and Cooling Sector: A Case Study for Italy. *Energies* 2017;10(10):1–33. URL: <https://ideas.repec.org/a/gam/jeners/v10y2017i10p1535-d114007.html>.
- [21] Krajačić, G., Duić, N., Zmijarević, Z., Mathiesen, B.V., Vučinić, A.A., da Graça Carvalho, M.. Planning for a 100% independent energy system based on smart energy storage for integration of renewables and CO2 emissions reduction. *Applied Thermal Engineering* 2011;31(13):2073–2083. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1359431111001463>. doi:10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2011.03.014.
- [22] Gota, D.I., Lund, H., Miclea, L.. A Romanian energy system model and a nuclear reduction strategy. *Energy* 2011;36(11):6413–6419. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544211006268>. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2011.09.029.

- [23] Kwon, P.S., Østergaard, P.A.. Comparison of future energy scenarios for Denmark: IDA 2050, CEESA (Coherent Energy and Environmental System Analysis), and Climate Commission 2050. *Energy* 2012;46(1):275–282. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544212006536>. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2012.08.022.
- [24] Connolly, D., Lund, H., Mathiesen, B.V.. Smart Energy Europe: The technical and economic impact of one potential 100% renewable energy scenario for the European Union. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2016;60:1634–1653. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032116002331>. doi:10.1016/j.rser.2016.02.025.
- [25] Hansen, K., Mathiesen, B.V., Skov, I.R.. Full energy system transition towards 100% renewable energy in Germany in 2050. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2019;102:1–13. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032118307913>. doi:10.1016/j.rser.2018.11.038.
- [26] Prina, M.G., Lionetti, M., Manzolini, G., Sparber, W., Moser, D.. Transition pathways optimization methodology through EnergyPLAN software for long-term energy planning. *Applied Energy* 2019;235:356–368. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306261918316672>. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.10.099.
- [27] Anjo, J., Neves, D., Silva, C., Shivakumar, A., Howells, M.. Modeling the long-term impact of demand response in energy planning: The Portuguese electric system case study. *Energy* 2018;165:456–468. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544218318553>. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2018.09.091.
- [28] Welsch, M., Deane, P., Howells, M., Ó Gallachóir, B., Rogan, F., Bazilian, M., et al. Incorporating flexibility requirements into long-term energy system models – A case study on high levels of renewable electricity penetration in Ireland. *Applied En-*

- ergy 2014;135:600–615. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306261914008836>. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2014.08.072.
- [29] Gardumi, F., Welsch, M., Howells, M., Colombo, E.. Representation of Balancing Options for Variable Renewables in Long-Term Energy System Models: An Application to OSeMOSYS. *Energies* 2019;12(12):2366. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/12/12/2366>. doi:10.3390/en12122366.
- [30] Navas-Anguita, Z., García-Gusano, D., Iribarren, D.. Prospective Life Cycle Assessment of the Increased Electricity Demand Associated with the Penetration of Electric Vehicles in Spain. *Energies* 2018;11(5):1185. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/11/5/1185>. doi:10.3390/en11051185.
- [31] García-Gusano, D., Martín-Gamboa, M., Iribarren, D., Dufour, J.. Prospective Analysis of Life-Cycle Indicators through Endogenous Integration into a National Power Generation Model. *Resources* 2016;5(4):39. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2079-9276/5/4/39>. doi:10.3390/resources5040039.
- [32] García-Gusano, D., Iribarren, D.. Prospective energy security scenarios in Spain: The future role of renewable power generation technologies and climate change implications. *Renewable Energy* 2018;126:202–209. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0960148118303550>. doi:10.1016/j.renene.2018.03.044.
- [33] Kumar, S., Madlener, R.. Energy systems and COP21 Paris climate agreement targets in Germany: an integrated modeling approach. In: 2018 7th International Energy and Sustainability Conference (IESC). 2018, p. 1–6. doi:10.1109/IESC.2018.8440004; iSSN: null.
- [34] Bartholdsen, H.K., Eidens, A., Löffler, K., Seehaus, F., Wejda, F., Burandt, T., et al. Pathways for Germany’s Low-Carbon Energy Transformation Towards 2050. *Energies* 2019;12(15):2988. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/12/15/2988>. doi:10.3390/en12152988.

- [35] Hainsch, K., Burandt, T., Kemfert, C., Löffler, K., Oei, P.Y., von Hirschhausen, C.. Emission Pathways Towards a Low-Carbon Energy System for Europe: A Model-Based Analysis of Decarbonization Scenarios. SSRN Scholarly Paper ID 3227733; Social Science Research Network; Rochester, NY; 2018. URL: <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=3227733>.
- [36] Colbertaldo, P., Guandalini, G., Campanari, S.. Modelling the integrated power and transport energy system: The role of power-to-gas and hydrogen in long-term scenarios for Italy. *Energy* 2018;154:592–601. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544218306960>. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2018.04.089.
- [37] Colbertaldo, P., Cerniauskas, S., Grube, T., Robinius, M., Stolten, D., Campanari, S.. Clean mobility infrastructure and sector integration in long-term energy scenarios: The case of Italy. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2020;133:110086. doi:10.1016/j.rser.2020.110086.
- [38] Teske, S., Morris, T., Nagrath, K.. 100% renewable energy: An energy [R] evolution for ITALY. Tech. Rep.; Institute for Sustainable Futures (ISF); 2020.
- [39] Vellini, M., Bellocchi, S., Gambini, M., Manno, M., Stilo, T.. Impact and costs of proposed scenarios for power sector decarbonisation: An Italian case study. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 2020;274:123667. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.123667.
- [40] Spiecker, S., Weber, C.. The future of the European electricity system and the impact of fluctuating renewable energy – A scenario analysis. *Energy Policy* 2014;65:185–197. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0301421513010549>. doi:10.1016/j.enpol.2013.10.032.
- [41] Pfenninger, S., Keirstead, J.. Renewables, nuclear, or fossil fuels? Scenarios for Great Britain’s power system considering costs, emissions and energy security. *Applied Energy* 2015;152:83–93. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306261915005656>. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2015.04.102.

- [42] Lombardi, F., Pickering, B., Colombo, E., Pfenninger, S.. Policy Decision Support for Renewables Deployment through Spatially Explicit Practically Optimal Alternatives. *Joule* 2020;4(10):2185–2207. doi:10.1016/j.joule.2020.08.002.
- [43] Bramstoft, R., Skytte, K.. Decarbonizing Sweden’s energy and transportation system by 2050. *International Journal of Sustainable Energy Planning and Management* 2017;14:3–20. URL: <https://journals.aau.dk/index.php/sepm/article/view/1828>. doi:10.5278/ijsepm.2017.14.2.
- [44] Pedersen, R.B.B., Skytte, K.. Decarbonising the Swedish transport sector with electricity or biofuels. In: Swedish Association for Energy Economics (SAEE) conference 2016. 2016, URL: <https://orbit.dtu.dk/en/publications/decarbonising-the-swedish-transport-sector-with-electricity-or-bi>.
- [45] Poncelet, K., Delarue, E., Six, D., Duerinck, J., D’haeseleer, W.. Impact of the level of temporal and operational detail in energy-system planning models. *Applied Energy* 2016;162:631–643. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306261915013276>. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2015.10.100.
- [46] Devogelaer, D.. Towards 100% renewable energy in Belgium by 2050. *Tech. Rep.*; 2012. URL: https://www.plan.be/uploaded/documents/201212190938210.Backcasting_2050_FinalReport_12_12_12.pdf.
- [47] Rečka, L., Ščasný, M.. Impacts of carbon pricing, brown coal availability and gas cost on Czech energy system up to 2050. *Energy* 2016;108:19–33. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S036054421501645X>. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2015.12.003.
- [48] Seljom, P., Rosenberg, E.. A Scandinavian Transition Towards a Carbon-Neutral Energy System. In: Giannakidis, G., Karlsson, K., Labriet, M., Gallachóir, B.Ó., editors. *Limiting Global Warming to Well Below 2 °C: Energy System Modelling and*

- Policy Development. Lecture Notes in Energy; Cham: Springer International Publishing. ISBN 978-3-319-74424-7; 2018, p. 105–121. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-74424-7_7.
- [49] Chiodi, A., Gargiulo, M., Rogan, F., Deane, J., Lavigne, D., Rout, U.K., et al. Modelling the impacts of challenging 2050 European climate mitigation targets on Ireland’s energy system. *Energy Policy* 2013;53:169–189. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0301421512009263>. doi:10.1016/j.enpol.2012.10.045.
- [50] Pursiheimo, E., Holttinen, H., Koljonen, T.. Path toward 100% renewable energy future and feasibility of power-to-gas technology in Nordic countries. *IET Renewable Power Generation* 2017;11(13):1695–1706. doi:10.1049/iet-rpg.2017.0021.
- [51] Petrović, S.N., Karlsson, K.B.. Residential heat pumps in the future Danish energy system. *Energy* 2016;114:787–797. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544216311100>. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2016.08.007.
- [52] Labriet, M., Cabal, H., Lechón, Y., Giannakidis, G., Kanudia, A.. The implementation of the EU renewable directive in Spain. Strategies and challenges. *Energy Policy* 2010;38(5):2272–2281. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0301421509009537>. doi:10.1016/j.enpol.2009.12.015.
- [53] Amorim, F., Pina, A., Gerbelová, H., Pereira da Silva, P., Vasconcelos, J., Martins, V.. Electricity decarbonisation pathways for 2050 in Portugal: A TIMES (The Integrated MARKAL-EFOM System) based approach in closed versus open systems modelling. *Energy* 2014;69:104–112. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0360544214000735>. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2014.01.052.
- [54] Fortes, P., Simoes, S.G., Gouveia, J.P., Seixas, J.. Electricity, the silver bullet for the deep decarbonisation of the energy system? Cost-effectiveness analysis for Portugal. *Applied Energy* 2019;237:292–303. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306261918318853>. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.12.067.

- [55] Fortes, P., Simões, S., Seixas, J., Regemorter, D.V., Ferreira, F.. Top-down and bottom-up modelling to support low-carbon scenarios: climate policy implications. *Climate Policy* 2013;13(3):285–304. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2013.768919>. doi:10.1080/14693062.2013.768919.
- [56] Krook Riekkola, A., Ahlgren, E.O., Söderholm, P.. Ancillary benefits of climate policy in a small open economy: The case of Sweden. *Energy Policy* 2011;39(9):4985–4998. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S030142151100471X>. doi:10.1016/j.enpol.2011.06.015.
- [57] Krakowski, V., Assoumou, E., Mazauric, V., Maïzi, N.. Feasible path toward 40–100% renewable energy shares for power supply in France by 2050: A prospective analysis. *Applied Energy* 2016;171:501–522. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306261916304251>. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.03.094.
- [58] Assoumou, E., Maïzi, N.. Carbon value dynamics for France: A key driver to support mitigation pledges at country scale. *Energy Policy* 2011;39(7):4325–4336. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0301421511003338>. doi:10.1016/j.enpol.2011.04.050.
- [59] Viridis, M.R.. Pathways to deep decarbonization in Italy. Tech. Rep.; 2015.
- [60] Pina, A., Silva, C.A., Ferrão, P.. High-resolution modeling framework for planning electricity systems with high penetration of renewables. *Applied Energy* 2013;112:215–223. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S030626191300487X>. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2013.05.074.
- [61] Tigas, K., Giannakidis, G., Mantzaris, J., Lalas, D., Sakellaris, N., Nakos, C., et al. Wide scale penetration of renewable electricity in the Greek energy system in view of the European decarbonization targets for 2050. *Renewable and Sustainable*

- Energy Reviews 2015;42:158–169. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032114008247>. doi:10.1016/j.rser.2014.10.007.
- [62] Simoes, S., Nijs, W., Ruiz, P., Sgobbi, A., Thiel, C.. Decarbonised pathways for a low carbon EU28 power sector until 2050. In: 11th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM14). 2014, p. 1–5. doi:10.1109/EEM.2014.6861232; iSSN: 2165-4077.
- [63] Moore, A., Price, J., Zeyringer, M.. The role of floating offshore wind in a renewable focused electricity system for Great Britain in 2050. Energy Strategy Reviews 2018;22:270–278. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2211467X18300920>. doi:10.1016/j.esr.2018.10.002.
- [64] Zeyringer, M., Price, J., Fais, B., Li, P.H., Sharp, E.. Designing low-carbon power systems for Great Britain in 2050 that are robust to the spatiotemporal and inter-annual variability of weather. Nature Energy 2018;3(5):395–403. URL: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41560-018-0128-x>. doi:10.1038/s41560-018-0128-x.
- [65] Pye, S.. Pathways to deep decarbonization in the United Kingdom. Tech. Rep.; 2015.
- [66] Usher, P., Strachan, N.. UK MARKAL Modelling - Examining Decarbonisation Pathways in the 2020s on the Way to Meeting the 2050 Emissions Target. Report; UCL Energy Institute, University College London; London, UK; 2011. URL: <http://www.theccc.org.uk/reports/fourth-carbon-budget/supporting-research>.
- [67] Ekins, P., Anandarajah, G., Strachan, N.. Towards a low-carbon economy: scenarios and policies for the UK. Climate Policy 2011;11(2):865–882. URL: <https://doi.org/10.3763/cpo1.2010.0126>. doi:10.3763/cpo1.2010.0126.
- [68] Ekins, P., Keppo, I., Skea, J., Strachan, N., Usher, W., Anandarajah, G.. The UK energy system in 2050: Comparing Low-Carbon, Resilient Scenarios. Tech. Rep.; 2013. URL: <http://www.ukerc.ac.uk/publications/>

the-uk-energy-system-in-2050-comparing-low-carbon-resilient-scenarios.html.

- [69] Li, F.G.N., Trutnevyte, E.. Investment appraisal of cost-optimal and near-optimal pathways for the UK electricity sector transition to 2050. *Applied Energy* 2017;189:89–109. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306261916318104>. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.12.047.
- [70] Anable, J., Brand, C., Tran, M., Eyre, N.. Modelling transport energy demand: A socio-technical approach. *Energy Policy* 2012;41:125–138. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S030142151000635X>. doi:10.1016/j.enpol.2010.08.020.
- [71] Decarbonizzazione dell'economia italiana. scenari di sviluppo del sistema energetico nazionale. Tech. Rep.; 2017. URL: http://www.dsctm.cnr.it/images/Eventi_img/de_carbonizzazione_3_ottobre_2017/RSE%20Decarbonizzazione_WEB.PDF.
- [72] Lanati, F., Gaeta, M.. How to achieve a complete decarbonization of the Italian energy system by 2050? In: 2020 17th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM). 2020, p. 1–5. doi:10.1109/EEM49802.2020.9221953.
- [73] Landis, F., Marcucci, A., Rausch, S., Kannan, R., Bretschger, L.. Multi-model comparison of Swiss decarbonization scenarios. *Swiss Journal of Economics and Statistics* 2019;155(1):12. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41937-019-0040-8>. doi:10.1186/s41937-019-0040-8.
- [74] Kannan, R., Turton, H.. Switzerland Energy Transition Scenarios – Development and Application of the Swiss TIMES Energy System Model (STEM). Tech. Rep.; 2014. URL: <https://www.psi.ch/sites/default/files/import/eem/PublicationsTabelle/2014-STEM-PSI-Bericht-14-06.pdf>. doi:10.13140/2.1.3935.3121.

- [75] Rodriguez, B.S., Drummond, P., Ekins, P.. Decarbonizing the EU energy system by 2050: an important role for BECCS. *Climate Policy* 2017;17(sup1):S93–S110. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2016.1242058>. doi:10.1080/14693062.2016.1242058.
- [76] Weidmann, N.O.. Transformation strategies towards a sustainable Swiss energy system: An energy-economic scenario analysis. Doctoral Thesis; ETH Zurich; 2013. URL: <https://www.research-collection.ethz.ch/handle/20.500.11850/71958>. doi:10.3929/ethz-a-009962867.
- [77] Siskos, P., Zazias, G., Petropoulos, A., Evangelopoulou, S., Capros, P.. Implications of delaying transport decarbonisation in the EU: A systems analysis using the PRIMES model. *Energy Policy* 2018;121:48–60. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S030142151830404X>. doi:10.1016/j.enpol.2018.06.016.
- [78] Capros, P., Tasios, N., De Vita, A., Mantzos, L., Paroussos, L.. Model-based analysis of decarbonising the EU economy in the time horizon to 2050. *Energy Strategy Reviews* 2012;1(2):76–84. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2211467X12000193>. doi:10.1016/j.esr.2012.06.003.
- [79] Romeo, L.M., Calvo, E., Valero, A., De Vita, A.. Electricity consumption and CO2 capture potential in Spain. *Energy* 2009;34(9):1341–1350. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544209001601>. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2009.04.035.
- [80] Capros, P., Paroussos, L., Fragkos, P., Tsani, S., Boitier, B., Wagner, F., et al. European decarbonisation pathways under alternative technological and policy choices: A multi-model analysis. *Energy Strategy Reviews* 2014;2(3):231–245. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2211467X13001053>. doi:10.1016/j.esr.2013.12.007.
- [81] Spataru, C., Drummond, P., Zafeiratou, E., Barrett, M.. Long-term scenarios

- for reaching climate targets and energy security in UK. *Sustainable Cities and Society* 2015;17:95–109. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2210670715000384>. doi:10.1016/j.scs.2015.03.010.
- [82] Barton, J., Davies, L., Dooley, B., Foxon, T.J., Galloway, S., Hammond, G.P., et al. Transition pathways for a UK low-carbon electricity system: Comparing scenarios and technology implications. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2018;82:2779–2790. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032117313801>. doi:10.1016/j.rser.2017.10.007.
- [83] Criqui, P. Pathways to deep decarbonization in France. Tech. Rep.; 2015. URL: http://deepdecarbonization.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/09/DDPP_FRA.pdf.
- [84] Child, M., Breyer, C., Bogdanov, D., Fell, H.J.. The role of storage technologies for the transition to a 100% renewable energy system in Ukraine. *Energy Procedia* 2017;135:410–423. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1876610217346180>. doi:10.1016/j.egypro.2017.09.513.
- [85] Pye, S., Sabio, N., Strachan, N.. An integrated systematic analysis of uncertainties in UK energy transition pathways. *Energy Policy* 2015;87:673–684. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S030142151400706X>. doi:10.1016/j.enpol.2014.12.031.
- [86] Palzer, A., Henning, H.M.. A comprehensive model for the German electricity and heat sector in a future energy system with a dominant contribution from renewable energy technologies – Part II: Results. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2014;30:1019–1034. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032113007818>. doi:10.1016/j.rser.2013.11.032.
- [87] Quiggin, D., Buswell, R.. The implications of heat electrification on national electrical supply-demand balance under published 2050 energy scenarios. *Energy*

- 2016;98:253–270. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544215016230>. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2015.11.060.
- [88] Sithole, H., Cockerill, T.T., Hughes, K.J., Ingham, D.B., Ma, L., Porter, R.T.J., et al. Developing an optimal electricity generation mix for the UK 2050 future. *Energy* 2016;100:363–373. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544216300019>. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2016.01.077.
- [89] Pfluger, B., Sensfuß, F., Schubert, G., Leisentritt, J.. Tangible ways towards climate protection in the European Union. Tech. Rep.; 2011.
- [90] Zappa, W., Junginger, M., van den Broek, M.. Is a 100% renewable European power system feasible by 2050? *Applied Energy* 2019;233-234:1027–1050. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306261918312790>. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.08.109.
- [91] Louis, J.N., Allard, S., Kotrotsou, F., Debusschere, V.. A multi-objective approach to the prospective development of the European power system by 2050. *Energy* 2020;191:116539. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544219322340>. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2019.116539.
- [92] Dagoumas, A.S., Barker, T.S.. Pathways to a low-carbon economy for the UK with the macro-econometric E3MG model. *Energy Policy* 2010;38(6):3067–3077. doi:10.1016/j.enpol.2010.01.047.
- [93] Tatarewicz, I., Lewarski, M., Skwierz, S.. Scenarios of low-emission energy sector for Poland and the EU until 2050. Tech. Rep.; 2019.
- [94] Haller, M., Ludig, S., Bauer, N.. Decarbonization scenarios for the EU and MENA power system: Considering spatial distribution and short term dynamics of renewable generation. *Energy Policy* 2012;47:282–290. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0301421512003746>. doi:10.1016/j.enpol.2012.04.069.

- [95] Jägemann, C., Fürsch, M., Hagspiel, S., Nagl, S.. Decarbonizing Europe's power sector by 2050 — Analyzing the economic implications of alternative decarbonization pathways. *Energy Economics* 2013;40:622–636. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0140988313001928>. doi:10.1016/j.eneco.2013.08.019.
- [96] Pleßmann, G., Blechinger, P.. Outlook on South-East European power system until 2050: Least-cost decarbonization pathway meeting EU mitigation targets. *Energy* 2017;137:1041–1053. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544217304516>. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2017.03.076.
- [97] Krajačić, G., Duić, N., Carvalho, M.d.G.. How to achieve a 100% RES electricity supply for Portugal? *Applied Energy* 2011;88(2):508–517. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306261910003703>. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2010.09.006.
- [98] Antosiewicz, M., Nikas, A., Szpor, A., Witajewski-Baltvilks, J., Doukas, H.. Pathways for the transition of the Polish power sector and associated risks. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions* 2019;URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2210422418302405>. doi:10.1016/j.eist.2019.01.008.
- [99] Jafari, M., Bompard, E., Delmastro, C., Botterud, A., Grosso, D.. *Electrify Italy: The role of renewable energy*. In: Gas. Boston, USA; 2019,.
- [100] Bompard, E., Botterud, A., Corgnati, S., Huang, T., Jafari, M., Leone, P., et al. An electricity triangle for energy transition: Application to Italy. *Applied Energy* 2020;277:115525. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.115525.
- [101] Barker, T., Scricciu, S.S.. Modeling low climate stabilization with E3MG: Towards a 'New Economics' approach to simulating energy-environment-economy system dynamics. *The Energy Journal* 2010;31(Special Issue).

- [102] Energy Exemplar, . PLEXOS Market Simulation Software. <https://energyexemplar.com/solutions/plexos/>; ????
- [103] Richter, J.. DIMENSION - A Dispatch and Investment Model for European Electricity Markets. Tech. Rep. 2011-3; Energiewirtschaftliches Institut an der Universitaet zu Koeln (EWI); 2011.
- [104] Pfenninger, S., Pickering, B.. Calliope: A multi-scale energy systems modelling framework. *Journal of Open Source Software* 2018;3(29):825. doi:10.21105/joss.00825.
- [105] Bogdanov, D., Breyer, C.. North-East Asian Super Grid for 100% renewable energy supply: Optimal mix of energy technologies for electricity, gas and heat supply options. *Energy Conversion and Management* 2016;112:176–190. doi:10.1016/j.enconman.2016.01.019.
- [106] Duić, N., Krajačić, G., da Graça Carvalho, M.. RenewIslands methodology for sustainable energy and resource planning for islands. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2008;12(4):1032–1062. doi:10.1016/j.rser.2006.10.015.
- [107] Jenkins, J.D., Sepulveda, N.A.. Enhanced Decision Support for a Changing Electricity Landscape: The GenX Configurable Electricity Resource Capacity Expansion Model. Working Paper; MIT Energy Initiative; 2017.
- [108] MARKAL. 2019. URL: <https://iea-etsap.org/index.php/etsaptool/model-generators/markal>.
- [109] Fishbone, L.G., Abilock, H.. Markal, a linear-programming model for energy systems analysis: Technical description of the bnl version. *International Journal of Energy Research* 1981;5(4):353–375. doi:10.1002/er.4440050406.
- [110] Loulou, R., Remme, U., Kanudia, A., Lehtila, A., Goldstein, G.. Documentation for the times model. *Energy Technology Systems Analysis Programme* 2005;.

- [111] 2019. URL: <https://iea-etsap.org/index.php/etsap-tools/model-generators/times>.
- [112] Connolly, D., Lund, H., Mathiesen, B., Leahy, M.. A review of computer tools for analysing the integration of renewable energy into various energy systems. *Applied Energy* 2010;87(4):1059–1082. URL: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0306261909004188>. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2009.09.026.
- [113] IEA-ETSAP, . A comparison of the TIMES and MARKAL models. Tech. Rep.; ????
- [114] UCL, . ETM-UCL. 2018. URL: <https://www.ucl.ac.uk/energy-models/models/etm-ucl>; library Catalog: www.ucl.ac.uk.
- [115] Solano Rodriguez, B., Pye, S.. Overview of the european TIMES model at university college london (ETM-UCL). Tech. Rep.; University College London; 2015.
- [116] The PRIMES Model. 2019. URL: http://www.e3mlab.eu/e3mlab/index.php?option=com_content&view=category&id=35%3Aprimes&Itemid=80&layout=default&lang=en.
- [117] Antoniou, Y., Capros, P.. Decision support system framework of the PRIMES energy model of the European Commission. *International Journal of Global Energy Issues* 1999;12(1/2/3/4/5/6):92. URL: <http://www.inderscience.com/link.php?id=823>. doi:10.1504/IJGEI.1999.000823.
- [118] EnergyPLAN | Advanced energy systems analysis computer model. 2018. URL: <https://www.energyplan.eu/>.
- [119] Lund, H.. EnergyPLAN - Advanced Energy Systems Analysis Computer Model. Tech. Rep.; Aalborg University, Denmark; 2015.
- [120] Panos, E.. Acceleration strategies for speeding up the solution time of the TIMES energy systems model generator. 2019.

- [121] E3MLab, . PRIMES MODEL - Detailed model description. Tech. Rep.; 2018.
- [122] Jalil-Vega, F., Hawkes, A.D.. The effect of spatial resolution on outcomes from energy systems modelling of heat decarbonisation. *Energy* 2018;155:339–350. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2018.04.160.
- [123] highRES |UCL. 2019. URL: <https://www.ucl.ac.uk/energy-models/models/highres>; library Catalog: www.ucl.ac.uk.
- [124] Pfenninger, S.. Energy scientists must show their workings. *Nature News* 2017;542(7642):393. URL: <http://www.nature.com/news/energy-scientists-must-show-their-workings-1.21517>. doi:10.1038/542393a; section: Column: World View.
- [125] Openmod - Open Energy Modelling Initiative. 2020. URL: <http://www.openmod-initiative.org/>.
- [126] Gitz, V., Sassi, O., Hourcade, J.C., Waisman, H., Guivarch, C.. IMACLIM-R: A modelling framework to simulate sustainable development pathways. *International Journal of Global Environmental Issues* 2010;10:5–24. doi:10.1504/IJGENVI.2010.030566.
- [127] Hourcade, J.C., Sassi, O., Crassous, R., Gitz, V., Waisman, H., Guivarch, C.. IMACLIM-R: a modelling framework to simulate sustainable development pathways. *International Journal of Global Environmental Issues* 2010;10(1/2):5–24. URL: <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-00566290>. doi:10.1504/IJGENVI.2010.030566.
- [128] Heaton, C.. Modelling Low-Carbon Energy System Designs with the ETI ESME Model. Tech. Rep.; 2014. URL: <https://www.eti.co.uk/library/modelling-low-carbon-energy-system-designs-with-the-eti-esme-model>.
- [129] OSeMOSYS - Home. 2019. URL: <http://www.osemosys.org/>.

- [130] Howells, M., Rogner, H., Strachan, N., Heaps, C., Huntington, H., Kypreos, S., et al. OSeMOSYS: The Open Source Energy Modeling System: An introduction to its ethos, structure and development. *Energy Policy* 2011;39(10):5850–5870. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0301421511004897>. doi:10.1016/j.enpol.2011.06.033.
- [131] Prina, M.G., Manzolini, G., Moser, D., Nastasi, B., Sparber, W.. Classification and challenges of bottom-up energy system models - A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2020;129:109917. doi:10.1016/j.rser.2020.109917.
- [132] Groissböck, M.. Are open source energy system optimization tools mature enough for serious use? *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2019;102:234–248. doi:10.1016/j.rser.2018.11.020.
- [133] Löffler, K., Hainsch, K., Burandt, T., Oei, P.Y., Kemfert, C., Von Hirschhausen, C.. Designing a Model for the Global Energy System—GENeSYS-MOD: An Application of the Open-Source Energy Modeling System (OSeMOSYS). *Energies* 2017;10(10):1468. doi:10.3390/en10101468.
- [134] Kotzur, L., Markewitz, P., Robinius, M., Stolten, D.. Time series aggregation for energy system design: Modeling seasonal storage. *Applied Energy* 2018;213:123–135. URL: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1710.07593>. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.01.023; arXiv: 1710.07593.
- [135] Welsch, M., Howells, M., Bazilian, M., DeCarolis, J.F., Hermann, S., Rogner, H.H.. Modelling elements of Smart Grids – Enhancing the OSeMOSYS (Open Source Energy Modelling System) code. *Energy* 2012;46(1):337–350. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2012.08.017.
- [136] Niet, T.A.. Mitigating risk of emissions in energy planning and the operational implications. Thesis; 2018.

- [137] Kuling, K., Niet, T.. A comparison of two different methods for modelling storage with OSeMOSYS. In: 43rd International Association of Energy Economics Conference. Paris, France; 2020,.
- [138] UK Department of Energy and Climate Change, . 2050 Calculator. <http://2050-calculator-tool.decc.gov.uk/>; ????
- [139] Münster, M., Larsen, H., Iversen, J.. STREAM manual. Tech. Rep.; DTU; 2015.
- [140] Codina Gironès, V., Moret, S., Maréchal, F., Favrat, D.. Strategic energy planning for large-scale energy systems: A modelling framework to aid decision-making. *Energy* 2015;90:173–186. URL: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544215007136>. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2015.06.008.
- [141] Pfenninger, S.. Dealing with multiple decades of hourly wind and PV time series in energy models: A comparison of methods to reduce time resolution and the planning implications of inter-annual variability. *Applied Energy* 2017;197:1–13. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.03.051.
- [142] Gabrielli, P., Gazzani, M., Martelli, E., Mazzotti, M.. Optimal design of multi-energy systems with seasonal storage. *Applied Energy* 2018;219:408–424. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.07.142.
- [143] Piano Nazionale Integrato Energia e Clima (PNIEC). 2019. URL: https://www.mise.gov.it/images/stories/documenti/PNIEC_finale_17012020.pdf; Mise, Italian Government.
- [144] Strategia Energetica Nazionale (SEN). 2017. URL: <https://www.mise.gov.it/images/stories/documenti/Testo-integrale-SEN-2017.pdf>; Mise, Italian Government.
- [145] Capros, P., De Vita, A., Tasios, N., Siskos, P., Kannavou, M.. EU reference scenario 2016. Energy, transport and GHG emissions : trends

- to 2050. 2016. URL: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/aed45f8e-63e3-47fb-9440-a0a14370f243/language-en/format-PDF/source-106883045>.
- [146] Baseline scenario of the heating and cooling demand in buildings and industry in the 14 MSs until 2050. 2017. URL: https://heatroadmap.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/HRE4_D3.3andD3.4.pdf; European Project n. 695989, D3.3 and D3.4, "Heat Roadmap Europe 4 (HRE4): Building the knowledge, skills, and capacity required to enable new policies and encourage new investments in the heating and cooling sector".
- [147] Terna - Dati statistici. 2019. URL: <http://www.terna.it/it-it/sistemmaelettrico/statisticheeprevisioni/datistatistici>.
- [148] Koffi, B., Cerutti, A., Duerr, M., Iancu, A., Kona, A., Janssens-Maenhout, G.. CoM Default Emission Factors for the Member States of the European Union. 2017.
- [149] Brown, T., Schlachtberger, D., Kies, A., Schramm, S., Greiner, M.. Synergies of sector coupling and transmission reinforcement in a cost-optimised, highly renewable European energy system. *Energy* 2018;160:720–739. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2018.06.222.
- [150] Moret, S., Babonneau, F., Bierlaire, M., Maréchal, F.. Overcapacity in European power systems: Analysis and robust optimization approach. *Applied Energy* 2020;259:113970. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.113970.
- [151] Moret, S., Babonneau, F., Bierlaire, M., Maréchal, F.. Decision support for strategic energy planning: A robust optimization framework. *European Journal of Operational Research* 2020;280(2):539–554. doi:10.1016/j.ejor.2019.06.015.
- [152] Brown, T., Hörsch, J., Schlachtberger, D.. PyPSA: Python for Power System Analysis. *Journal of Open Research Software* 2018;6(1):4. doi:10.5334/jors.188.

- [153] Kavvadias, K., Hidalgo Gonzalez, I., Zucker, A., Quoilin, S.. Integrated modelling of future EU power and heat systems-The Dispa-SET v2. 2 open-source model. Tech. Rep.; Publications Office of the European Union; European Commission; 2018.
- [154] Craig, P.P., Gadgil, A., Koomey, J.G.. What can history teach us? A retrospective examination of long-term energy forecasts for the united states. Annual Review of Energy and the Environment 2002;27(1):83–118. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.energy.27.122001.083425>. doi:10.1146/annurev.energy.27.122001.083425. arXiv:<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.energy.27.122001.083425>.
- [155] Bilancio Energetico Nazionale (BEN). Tech. Rep.; Ministero dello Sviluppo Economico (MISE); 2015. URL: <https://dgsaie.mise.gov.it/ben.php>.
- [156] Rapporto Statistico. Energia da fonti rinnovabili in Italia. Tech. Rep.; Gestore dei Servizi Energetici (GSE); 2015. URL: https://www.gse.it/documenti_site/Documenti%20GSE/Rapporti%20statistici/Rapporto%20statistico%20GSE%20-%202015.pdf.
- [157] Bozzetto, S., Pezzaglia, M., Rossi, L., Pecorino, B.. Considerazioni sul potenziale del “biogas fatto bene” italiano ottenuto dalla digestione anaerobica di matrici agricole. 2016. URL: <http://www.consorziobiogas.it/publicazioni-in-evidenza.htm>.
- [158] Il riscaldamento urbano. ANNUARIO 2016. Tech. Rep.; Associazione Italiana Riscaldamento Urbano (AIRU); 2016.
- [159] Serie storica delle emissioni di gas serra 1990-2017. Tech. Rep.; ISPRA; 2019. URL: <http://www.sinanet.isprambiente.it/it/sia-ispra/serie-storiche-emissioni/serie-storiche-delle-emissioni-di-gas-serra/view>.